

ECP 2006 DILI 510049

ENRICH

**Report on the Documentation and Use
of the ENRICH Garage Engine and on Best Practice in handling
of
Unicode and Non-Unicode Data**

Deliverable number	D-3.4
Dissemination level	Public
Delivery date	1 st December 2009
Status	Final
Author(s)	James Cummings, Tomasz Parkoła, Mariusz Stanisławczyk, Marcin Werla and Tomáš Psohlavec

eContentplus

This project is funded under the *eContentplus* programme¹,
a multiannual Community programme to make digital content in Europe more accessible,
usable and exploitable.

¹ OJ L 79, 24.3.2005, p. 1.

Document Version Control

Version	Date	Change Made (and if appropriate reason for change)	Initials of Commentator(s) or Author(s)
0.0	25 Oct 09	Draft Deliverable	JC, OUCS PSNC TP, AIP
1.0.	1 Dec 09	Final Version	OUCS, PSNC, AIP
2.0	14 Dec 09	Reviewed Final Version – changes done according to recommendations and comments done by Torsten Schassan	OUCS

Document Review

Reviewer	Institution	Date and result of the review
Tomas Psohlavec	AIP	15 November 2009, the content of the deliverable approved
Jakub Heller	CCP	1 December 2009, the deliverable formally checked and approved
Torsten Schassan	Herzog August Bibliothek	Several comments and recommendations done as summarized in the Progress Report

Approved By (signature)	Date

Accepted by at European Commission (signature)	Date

Introduction

This deliverable covers two relatively independent tasks realized during the second year of the ENRICH project in frame of WP3. Therefore we decided to keep its structure divided into two parts: the first one dealing with ENRICH Garage Engine developed in WP3 instead of originally intended tools for assurance of METS/TEI interoperability (the detailed explanation can be found in the chapter 2 of Part 1) and the second one dealing with UNICODE and non-UNICODE characters in Manuscriptorium. We believe that this structure allows better understanding of what has been done and is more reader-friendly. Both parts are therefore structured as common deliverables with separate Summary, Content and Conclusions.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

INTRODUCTION.....	3
PART 1: REPORT ON THE DOCUMENTATION AND USE OF THE ENRICH GARAGE ENGINE ..	7
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2 ENRICH GARAGE ENGINE AS A REPLACEMENT DELIVERABLE.....	10
3 THE BACKGROUND OF THE ENRICH GARAGE ENGINE	10
4 INTRODUCTION TO THE EGE FRAMEWORK.....	12
5 INTRODUCTION TO THE EGE WEB CLIENT	13
5.1 USING THE EGE WEB CLIENT	13
5.2 CONVERTING FILES WITH THE EGE WEB CLIENT.....	14
5.2.1 <i>Selecting Input Type</i>	15
5.2.2 <i>Selecting Conversion Path</i>	15
5.2.3 <i>Conversion Profiles</i>	16
5.2.4 <i>Converting Your File</i>	16
5.3 VALIDATING FILES WITH THE EGE WEB CLIENT.....	16
5.3.1 <i>Selecting Input Type</i>	16
5.3.2 <i>Validating Your File</i>	17
6 INTERNAL MECHANISMS OF THE EGE.....	17
6.1 EGE INTERNAL MECHANISMS: A CASE STUDY	17
6.2 SUMMARY	20
7 OVERVIEW OF THE EGE API.....	21
7.1 EGE API SPECIFIC DATA TYPES (PL.PSNC.DLTEAM.EGE.TYPES).....	21
7.2 COMPONENTS INTERFACES	24
7.3 RECOGNIZER.....	24
7.4 VALIDATOR	24
7.5 CONVERTER.....	25
7.6 CONFIGURABLECONVERTER.....	25
7.7 EGE INTERFACE AND IMPLEMENTATION	25
8 CREATING EGE EXTENSIONS	27
8.1.1 <i>Step 1: Java code</i>	27
8.1.2 <i>Step 2 : JPF Descriptor</i>	31
8.1.3 <i>Creating other extensions</i>	32
9 XSL CONVERTER CONFIGURATION.....	33
9.1 INTRODUCTION	33
9.2 MODIFYING THE 'PLUGIN.XML' DESCRIPTOR FILE (ADDING A NEW XSL TRANSFORMATION).....	34
10 EGE CONVERSION AND VALIDATION RESTFUL WEB SERVICE INTERFACE	36
10.1 INTRODUCTION	36
10.2 CONVERSION	36
10.2.1 <i>'List input data types' operation</i>	36
10.2.2 <i>List conversion paths' operation</i>	37
10.2.3 <i>'Convert' operation</i>	38
10.3 EXAMPLE USE CASE.	40
10.3.1 <i>Step 1 : list of data types</i>	41
10.3.2 <i>Step 2 : list conversions paths</i>	41
10.3.3 <i>Step 3 : handling "list of conversions paths" response.</i>	41
10.3.4 <i>Step 4 : setting conversion properties.</i>	42

10.3.5	<i>Step 5 : performing conversion</i>	42
10.4	VALIDATION	42
10.4.1	<i>'List input data types' operation</i>	42
10.4.2	<i>'Validation' operation</i>	43
10.5	ERROR RESPONSE	44
11	DOWNLOAD	44
12	INSTALLING AND CONFIGURING EGE WEB PACKAGE	45
12.1	INSTALLING THE EGE	45
12.2	CONFIGURING OF THE EGE	45
13	EGE CASE STUDIES AND TESTING	46
14	CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	48
PART 2: REPORT ON BEST PRACTICE IN HANDLING OF UNICODE AND NON-UNICODE DATA		50
1	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	51
2	INTRODUCTION	52
3	CHARACTER SETS AND ENCODING	52
3.1	TERMINOLOGY AND KEY CONCEPTS	52
3.2	UNICODE AND XML	54
3.3	NON-UNICODE CHARACTERS AND XML	54
3.4	NORMALIZATION AND STANDARDIZATION	55
4	REPRESENTATION OF NON-STANDARD CHARACTERS	55
4.1	DESCRIPTIVE INFORMATION FOR NON-STANDARD CHARACTERS	56
4.2	ANNOTATION OF NON-STANDARD CHARACTERS	57
5	THE ENRICH PROJECT AND NON-STANDARD CHARACTERS	57
5.1	THE ENRICH gBANK AND THE MEDIEVAL UNICODE FONT INITIATIVE	58
5.2	ENRICH gBANK IN THE MANUSCRIPTORIUM SYSTEM	58
5.3	gBANK END-USER INTERFACE	58
5.4	gBANK API INTERFACE	61
5.5	INDEXING AND SEARCHING WITH THE gBANK	62
5.5.1	<i>Indexing with gBank Characters</i>	62
5.5.2	<i>Searching with gBank Characters</i>	62
5.5.3	<i>Advanced Search Features Using gBank Characters</i>	63
5.5.4	<i>Support of gBank in the Presentation Layer</i>	63
5.5.5	<i>Use of Images and Standardized Mappings</i>	63
5.5.6	<i>Use of TTF and CSS 3</i>	64
6	CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS	66
7	APPENDICES	67
7.1	APPENDIX A (A) STRUCTURAL LIGATURES	67
14.1	APPENDIX B (B) NON-STRUCTURAL LIGATURES	69
14.2	APPENDIX C SUBRANGE 2: SMALL CAPITALS	75
14.3	APPENDIX D SUBRANGE 3: ENLARGED MINUSCULES	76
14.4	APPENDIX E SUBRANGE 4: BASE-LINE ABBREVIATION CHARACTERS	80
14.5	APPENDIX F SUBRANGE 5: MODIFIED BASE-LINE ABBREVIATION CHARACTERS	81
14.6	APPENDIX G SUBRANGE 6: COMBINING MARKS	83
14.7	APPENDIX H SUBRANGE 7: COMBINING SUPERSCRIPIT CHARACTERS	85
14.8	APPENDIX I SUBRANGE 8: PUNCTUATION MARKS	88

14.9	APPENDIX J SUBRANGE 9: CRITICAL AND EPIGRAPHICAL SIGNS	90
14.10	APPENDIX K SUBRANGE 10: METRICAL SYMBOLS	91
14.11	APPENDIX L SUBRANGE 11: ADDITIONAL NUMBER FORMS	94
14.12	APPENDIX M SUBRANGE 12: WEIGHT, CURRENCY AND MEASUREMENT	95
14.13	APPENDIX N SUBRANGE 13: MODIFIED BASE-LINE CHARACTERS	97
14.14	APPENDIX O SUBRANGE 15: CHARACTERS WITH MACRON OR OVERLINE	98
14.15	APPENDIX P SUBRANGE 16: CHARACTERS WITH ACUTE ACCENT	108
14.16	APPENDIX Q SUBRANGE 17: CHARACTERS WITH DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT	117
14.17	APPENDIX R SUBRANGE 18: CHARACTERS WITH DOT ABOVE	125
14.18	APPENDIX S SUBRANGE 19: CHARACTERS WITH DOT BELOW	134
7.2	APPENDIX T SUBRANGE 20: CHARACTERS WITH DIAERESIS	144
14.19	APPENDIX U SUBRANGE 21: CHARACTERS WITH CURL ABOVE (REVERSED OGONEK)	147
14.20	APPENDIX V SUBRANGE 22: CHARACTERS WITH OGONEK	151
14.21	APPENDIX W SUBRANGE 23: CHARACTERS WITH BREVE	153
14.22	APPENDIX X SUBRANGE 24: CHARACTERS WITH BREVE BELOW	154
14.23	APPENDIX Y SUBRANGE 25: CHARACTERS WITH CIRCUMFLEX	155
14.24	APPENDIX Z SUBRANGE 26: CHARACTERS WITH RING ABOVE	157
14.25	APPENDIX AA SUBRANGE 27: CHARACTERS WITH RING BELOW	158
14.26	APPENDIX AB SUBRANGE 28: CHARACTERS WITH TILDE	159
14.27	APPENDIX AC SUBRANGE 29: CHARACTERS WITH CURLY BAR ABOVE	160
14.28	APPENDIX AD SUBRANGE 30: CHARACTERS WITH VERTICAL BAR ABOVE	161
14.29	APPENDIX AE SUBRANGE 31: CHARACTERS WITH SUPERSCRIPIT LETTERS	162
14.30	APPENDIX AF SUBRANGE 32: CHARACTERS WITH ACUTE ACCENT AND DOT ABOVE	172
14.31	APPENDIX AG SUBRANGE 33: CHARACTERS WITH ACUTE ACCENT AND DOT BELOW	176
14.32	APPENDIX AH SUBRANGE 34: CHARACTERS WITH ACUTE ACCENT AND DIAERESIS	177
14.33	APPENDIX AI SUBRANGE 35: CHARACTERS WITH ACUTE ACCENT AND CURL ABOVE (REVERSED OGONEK)	178
14.34	APPENDIX AJ SUBRANGE 36: CHARACTERS WITH ACUTE ACCENT AND OGONEK	179
14.35	APPENDIX AK SUBRANGE 37: CHARACTERS WITH DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT AND OGONEK	182
14.36	APPENDIX AL SUBRANGE 38: CHARACTERS WITH DOT ABOVE AND OGONEK	184
14.37	APPENDIX AM SUBRANGE 39: CHARACTERS WITH DOT BELOW AND OGONEK	186
14.38	APPENDIX AN SUBRANGE 40: CHARACTERS WITH DIAERESIS AND MACRON	188
14.39	APPENDIX AO SUBRANGE 41: CHARACTERS WITH DIAERESIS AND CIRCUMFLEX	189
14.40	APPENDIX AP SUBRANGE 42: CHARACTERS WITH DIAERESIS AND DOT BELOW	191
14.41	APPENDIX AQ SUBRANGE 43: CHARACTERS WITH OGONEK AND CURL ABOVE (REVERSED OGONEK)	192
7.3	APPENDIX AR SUBRANGE 44: CHARACTERS WITH OGONEK AND CIRCUMFLEX	193
14.42	APPENDIX AS SUBRANGE 45: CHARACTERS WITH RING ABOVE AND CIRCUMFLEX	194
7.4	APPENDIX AT SUBRANGE 46: CHARACTERS WITH MACRON AND BREVE	194
14.43	APPENDIX AU SUBRANGE 47: CHARACTERS WITH MACRON AND ACUTE ACCENT	199
7.5	APPENDIX AV SUBRANGE 48: CHARACTERS WITH OGONEK, DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE ACCENT	202
14.44	APPENDIX AW SUBRANGE 51: ALPHABETICAL LIST OF VARIANT LETTER FORMS	204

Part 1:

**Report on the Documentation and Use of the ENRICH Garage
Engine**

1 Executive Summary

The ENRICH Garage Engine (EGE) is a set of web tools for the conversion and validation of documents. It has both a web frontend and a RESTful web service API. This deliverable and indeed this report is a replacement for the original task and report as the first part of deliverable 3.4 of the ENRICH project. The original report related to the incorporation of METS and TEI together in the manuscriptorium framework, but the workpackage discovered that this was not necessary (the ENRICH TEI Specification catered for all the necessary metadata) needed for the manuscriptorium platform. More detail concerning this replacement is available in the Sections "ENRICH Garage Engine as a replacement deliverable" and "The background of the ENRICH Garage Engine" below. This report provides documentation for the EGE software which is released freely under an open source licence (GPL version 3). An introduction to the EGE Framework describes the basic concepts of how formats can be migrated through multiple transformative steps. This is then followed by an introduction to the EGE Web Client, a user-friendly web interface allowing format transformation based on predefined profiles. The report then delves a bit deeper in to the internal mechanisms of the EGE and how it works, followed by an overview of the EGE API. The creation of EGE Extensions to add additional functionality is documented along with the necessary XSL Converter Configuration. The EGE is available as a RESTful Web Service interface and the interaction with this for both conversion and validation of documents is detailed. The report concludes with information on downloading as well as installing and configuring the EGE web package under Apache Tomcat. This is followed by some final conclusions and recommendations. The recommendations of this report are:

This report would like to make the following five recommendations:

1. The stylesheets used for transformations in the EGE are sufficient for their usage in the ENRICH project. However, for greater use by other projects additional development should be encouraged of these transformations including further development for additional use cases and greater documentation on the extensibility and customisation of the underlying stylesheets. It is recommended that any additional development work in format migration and conversion be used to improve the existing EGE solution.
2. Increased development should also be considered for new stylesheets for additional formats (such as MARC) since the addition of a single new stylesheet then plugs into the EGE to allow a number of news transformation paths. It is recommended that where new format migration and conversion stylesheets are being developed for future projects, that these do so in a manner compatible with the EGE framework so that they may hopefully be incorporated into it.
3. The EGE is a coordinated RESTful web service framework that uses a documented API for interaction. Projects producing web-based software should use approaches that allow access to such APIs for building services on them, here demonstrated by the ENRICH EGE Web Client. Linking together of these individual web services to a greater whole is a roadmap for richer and more robust web applications. It is recommended that projects developing web-based software should produce a RESTful web service API and build and front-end systems on top of this.

4. The EGE is an open extensible system which one is able to customise to individual project needs. It is also open source, released under the GPL version 3 licence. Where possible it is recommended that software be open source and built in a manner that encourages extended and improving that software.
5. TEI P5 XML, here used as the ENRICH TEI P5 Specification, is not only a good format for the representation of textual materials and metadata, but is also sufficient as an intermediate format in a conversion pathway between two disparate formats. TEI P5 XML is recommended for any similar endeavours undertaken at a later date.

2 ENRICH Garage Engine as a replacement deliverable

The inclusion of the ENRICH Garage Engine (EGE) and its documentation is as a replacement deliverable in the context of the ENRICH project. When the original description of work was undertaken it was assumed that Manuscriptorium would move to a system that required METS containerization. Thus task 3.3 was set out as “Enhancement of internal environment of Manuscriptorium through implementation of METS containerization of the Manuscriptorium Scheme”. In investigating this task, OUCS and AIP discovered that because of the consequent developments in the TEI P5 ODD Specification created for the ENRICH project, and the adoption of this Specification for the internal Manuscriptorium Scheme, that the use of METS inside Manuscriptorium was not necessary for the limited use of METS that Manuscriptorium would have made. The aspects of METS that ENRICH intended to have leveraged are now catered for in the ENRICH TEI P5 specification, and it was deemed more beneficial for long-term preservation to keep to a single specification. OUCS found that the investigation phase of this task was still useful in that it identified concretely that METS was not required in this instance. METS may be useful to further development of manuscriptorium at a later date, but to accomplish the goals of the ENRICH project it was unnecessary and might introduce undesired extra complexity for very little gain at the moment. Simultaneously, having developed migration tools as part of task 3.1 and reporting on them in deliverable 3.3, it was decided that as part of WP3 OUCS will develop a new conversion tool framework with the remaining time left in task 3.3. This set of web services is called the ENRICH Garage Engine (EGE) would be designed to assist in the conversion, transformation, and validation of ENRICH data to other formats. This includes not only migration from legacy formats but transformations of ENRICH data to and from other applications such as MSWord. The EGE web services have been produced by PSNC. All software produced as part of this task has been publicly released under an open source license (GPL version 3 in the case of the EGE). This has (more than) replaced the time originally budgeted for the remainder of task 3.3 and the portion of the deliverable (D 3.4 part 1) concerning METS/TEI interoperability is instead replaced by the documentation on the development and use of the EGE. The report on the handling of Unicode and non-Unicode data in Manuscriptorium and TEI P5 conversions will remain unchanged as part of that deliverable (D 3.4 part 2). More information about the EGE is available at <http://dl.psnc.pl/software/EGE/>.

3 The background of the ENRICH Garage Engine

The ENRICH Garage Engine (EGE) is a migration tool technology which was not conceived for the original Description of Work for the ENRICH project but has now been developed by the PSNC ENRICH Partner as part of WP3. This tool is a Java-based format migration engine accessible in a number of different manners, such as through a web-form or directly via a RESTful API, which will facilitate the migration of legacy data through a number of different formats. Partly it builds on work that the TEI has done for the International Standards Organization (ISO), in seamlessly round-tripping ISO standards documents from Microsoft Word to TEI P5 XML and back again. The EGE allows users to submit a document for conversion to another format, and it will be analyzed, recognized as a particular type, converted, validated, and returned in a user-friendly manner. This builds upon a number

of existing stylesheets and conversions to allow conversion through multiple formats using an intermediate formats. The EGE was a recommended development of the report of ENRICH D3.3 on format migration and is discussed in more detail there.

4 Introduction to the EGE framework

The EGE is a major part of the ENRICH Garage system; its implementation is responsible for the management of conversions, transformations and validations of data performed by the ENRICH Garage. Conversions, transformations and validations are performed by a set of plug-ins compatible with the EGE plug-in specification. The software was initially created by the PSNC and OUCS as a part of the ENRICH project funded by the European Commission. EGE is distributed under an open-source license.

The EGE is a framework. It provides definitions of plug-ins (building blocks) which can be used in combination to perform a series of operations. There is also the API that can be used by other applications utilizing EGE. The image below presents the overview of the EGE architecture.

The use of the EGE is possible via the EGE API, which allows a program to:

- discover the functionality available for a particular data format that EGE provides with a current set of plug-ins;
- perform those available operations (e.g. conversion).

There are three basic types of EGE plug-ins: Recognizer, Converter and Validator.

- **Recognizer** - this plug-in is responsible for the recognition of the Internet Media Type (MIME type) of the given input data. For example, it will receive the input data and state that the input data has text/xml MIME type. The recognized data may then be further validated to check the format of the data.
- **Validator** - this plug-in is responsible for validation of the input data. For example it may be used to validate the ENRICH TEI P5 data stored in a MIME type (e.g. text/xml) either received from end user or created by one of the converters. The

following notation is assumed: ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml) - it means that validator is able to validate ENRICH TEI P5 format encoded in text/xml.

- **Converter** - this plug-in is responsible for converting the input data. It may be, for example, conversion from XML to Word, conversion from Word to PDF, conversion of the XML from one form to another (e.g. MASTER -> ENRICH TEI P5) or even cleaning the input data (e.g. removing redundant information).

The idea is that there may be a number of implementations for each particular plug-in type (e.g. two recognizers, five converters and three validators) connected to EGE instance. Plug-ins are connected to the EGE automatically at the start time and can be combined to perform complex iterative operations. The extensions mechanism is based on the Java Plugin Framework (<http://jpf.sourceforge.net/>) library. Thanks to this approach it is possible for other interested parties to extend the EGE if desired.

5 Introduction to the EGE Web Client

The ENRICH EGE Web Client gives an easy to use front end for exploiting the abilities of the ENRICH EGE. The ENRICH EGE is responsible for the management of conversions, transformations and validations of data performed by the ENRICH Garage. Conversions, transformations and validations are performed by a set of plug-ins compatible with the EGE plug-in specification. The software was initially created by the PSNC and OUCS as a part of the ENRICH project funded by the European Commission. EGE is distributed under an open-source license. It is straightforward and intuitive for users and has a clear progression through the steps needed to transform a document from one format to another. The EGE Web Client is a user-friendly frontend for the EGE Web Service but if one was converting many files, or doing so automatically as part of another process, it might be more appropriate to use the web service instead.

5.1 Using the EGE Web Client

The EGE Web Client should already have been set up and running as a web application, all interaction with the EGE Web Client is through a web browser, no extra software should be needed, however javascript must be enabled. To use the EGE Web Client you go to the appropriate URL. In the case of the ENRICH project this is: <http://dlibra.psnc.pl/ege-webclient/> for the time being. If this has not been set up, please go to the [Download page](#) .

This webpage contains three tabs 'Conversion', 'Validation' and 'Help'. The last of these links through to the help documentation, while the first two are where one can undertake to use the main functions of the EGE Web Client.

5.2 Converting Files with the EGE Web Client

The EGE Web Client allows you to convert documents from one format to another, possibly using an intermediate format before a second conversion. To know what forms of document it can convert to, the EGE Web Client needs to establish what format the input document is in. Once it knows this it can offer a conversion path, and allow a choice between multiple conversion profiles, before converting your file.

The screenshot shows the 'Conversion' tab of the EGE Web Client. At the top, there are three tabs: 'Conversion', 'Validation', and 'Help'. Below the tabs, a text box displays the currently selected path: `I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml(TEI Converter)->I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/xhtml+xml(TEI Converter)`.

Under 'Select input type:', there are four radio button options:

- [TEI,text/xml](#)
- [TEI,application/msword](#)
- [MASTER,text/xml](#)
- [EAD,text/xml](#)

Under 'Select conversion path:', there are four radio button options:

- [I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml\(TEI Converter\)](#)
- [I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml\(TEI Converter\)->I:TEI,text/xml/O:FO,text/xml\(TEI Converter\)](#)
- [I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml\(TEI Converter\)->I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/x-latex\(TEI Converter\)](#)
- [I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml\(TEI Converter\)->I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/xhtml+xml\(TEI Converter\)](#)

There are two sections for 'Conversion path parameters':

Section 1: Path vertex parameters : `I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml(TEI Converter)`
Select conversion profile:

Section 2: Path vertex parameters : `I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/xhtml+xml(TEI Converter)`
Select conversion profile:

At the bottom, there is a 'Specify file to convert:' section with a text input field, a 'Browse...' button, and a 'Convert' button.

5.2.1 Selecting Input Type

The EGE Web Client allows you to specify an input document's type from a list of choices predefined by the conversions that have been installed into that instance of the EGE Web Client. In the case of the ENRICH EGE Web Client conversion service these are:

- TEI,text/xml
- TEI,application/msword
- MASTER,text/xml
- EAD,text/xml

This takes the format of:

```
FORMAT,INTERNET MIME TYPE (IMT)
```

So in the case of the ENRICH EGE Web Client conversion service there are three formats TEI, MASTER, and EAD, and only two different IMT's text/xml and application/msword that it knows how to handle as input types. The EGE will test and validate your document after uploading it against its definition for the format you select.

Please note that the MS Word format referred to here is the DOCX format. Earlier word formats will cause an error.

5.2.2 Selecting Conversion Path

The conversion path is the route through which the EGE can transform your documents to other formats. This may simply be a single conversion or involve more than one steps. For example, having chosen 'TEI,text/xml' as the input type, one of the options available to us for conversion is:

```
I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/msword(TEI Converter)
```

The 'I:' section of this path indicates the IMT input type of the document to be converted. In this case it is "TEI,text/xml". This is followed by the output format indicated by 'O:'. In this case that format is: "TEI,application/msword(TEI Converter)". This shows that our input document which is in TEI XML will be converted to MS Word using the TEI converter (which transforms TEI files to the docx format). The reverse of this would be from MS Word to TEI:

```
I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml(TEI Converter)
```

One of the great strengths of the EGE is that it allows multiple transformations through a variety of formats. For example, the following path:

```
I:TEI,application/msword/O:TEI,text/xml(TEI Converter) ->  
I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/xhtml+xml(TEI Converter)
```

details the conversion path from an MS Word document to TEI XML, and then (after the arrow '->' indicating a second step in the path), the XML that results from the first transformation becomes the input to a conversion from TEI XML to XHTML.

5.2.3 Conversion Profiles

Beneath the selection of a conversion the EGE Web Client gives you the opportunity to modify the conversion path parameters through the selection of a predefined conversion profile. In the ENRICH EGE Web Client this gives you a choice between 'default', 'enrich' and 'iso' conversion profiles. One drop-down selection box for a profile will appear for each major step in the chosen conversion path. If you have not set up any conversion profiles for your own project, then using 'default' is probably the most sensible.

5.2.4 Converting Your File

Underneath where you select the conversion profiles you are prompted to "Specify file to convert:" and there is a 'Browse' but to look through your computer's file system to find a file of the selected input type to convert. Make sure that the document you select is in the correct format, and click on the 'Convert' button.

If your file has been converted successfully, you will be prompted to download it. If it has failed to convert and error message will be displayed. Make a note of this error message for any bug report you want to submit before trying again after ensure the correct input format has been chosen.

5.3 Validating Files with the EGE Web Client

In addition to converting your files, the EGE can simply be used to validate your files to ensure they are the correct input format. This takes place automatically when you upload your files for conversion, but it is also available as a separate feature on a second tab in the EGE Web Client.

The screenshot shows the 'Validation' tab of the EGE Web Client. At the top, there are three tabs: 'Conversion', 'Validation', and 'Help'. Below the tabs, the text 'Select input type:' is followed by three radio button options: 'TEI,text/xml' (which is selected), 'MASTER,text/xml', and 'EAD,text/xml'. Below this, the text 'Select file :' is followed by an empty text input field and a 'Browse...' button. At the bottom left, there is a 'Validate' button.

5.3.1 Selecting Input Type

Similar to the 'Conversion' tab, the EGE Web Client validation service allows you to specify an input document's type from a list of choices predefined by the conversions that have been installed into that instance of the EGE Web Client. In the case of the ENRICH EGE Web Client these are:

- TEI,text/xml
- MASTER,text/xml

- EAD,text/xml

Note that MS Word is not an option for validation because the validation method deals with 'text/xml' files. So in the case of the ENRICH EGE Web Client validation service there are three formats TEI, MASTER, and EAD, and only one IMT's "text/xml" that it knows how to handle as input types. The EGE will test and validate your document after uploading it against its definition for the format you select.

5.3.2 Validating Your File

Underneath where you select the conversion profiles you are prompted to "Select file:" to validate and there is a 'Browse' but to look through your computer's file system to find a file of the selected input type to validate. Make sure that the document you select is in the correct format, and click on the 'Validate' button.

If your file has been validated successfully a message will appear indicating this success. If it has failed to validate the error message will be displayed. Make a note of this error message for any bug report you want to submit and correcting whatever the error is before trying again after ensuring the correct input format has been chosen.

6 Internal mechanisms of the EGE

Having read the overview of the EGE it is now possible to proceed with the idea of the internal mechanism. This will lead to specification of the EGE API which is available for use in external applications. This will also show the potential possibilities of the EGE in case, when there will be a number of implementations of particular components types. Below you will find a simple case study illustrating EGE internal mechanism.

6.1 EGE internal mechanisms: a case study

Let us assume that:

1. Initially we have recognizers which are able to recognize text/xml, application/pdf and application/msword. Recognizers allow us to recognize the Internet MIME Type (IMT) of the input data.
2. We assume that we have the following validators: MASTER (text/xml), TEI P5 (text/xml), ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml), ENRICH TEI P5 (application/pdf), ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword), EAD (text/xml). Validators allow us to validate recognized data and therefore state the format of the input data.
3. The available set of converters is described in the table below. The X mark in the table means that we have converter which is able to convert from the format specified in the row name to the format specified in the column name.

To	MASTER (text/xml)	TEI P5 (text/xml)	ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml)	ENRICH TEI P5 (application /mword)	ENRICH TEI P5 (application /pdf)
From					
MASTER (text/xml)		X	X		
TEI P5 (text/xml)		X	X		
ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml)				X	
ENRICH TEI P5 (application /mword)			X		X
EAD (text/xml)	X		X		

Therefore with the above set of converters it is, for example, possible to convert from MASTER (text/xml) to TEI P5 (text/xml) and from ENRICH TEI P5 (application/mword) to ENRICH TEI P5 (application/pdf), but it is not possible to convert from EAD (text/xml) to ENRICH TEI P5 (application/pdf) or from TEI P5 (text/xml) to ENRICH TEI P5 (application/pdf). Additionally, we may imagine a converter from TEI P5 (text/xml) to TEI P5 (text/xml) which could simply clean the given input data of redundant information or restructure it in some pre-determined manner. Moreover, we could imagine a converter which will be independent of the format and will focus only on the IMT, e.g. converter which converts everything from (application/mword) to (application/pdf), although at this moment such feature is not supported.

Based on these three assumptions, let us build a directed graph of possible conversion, just as it is being built in the EGE. The nodes in the graph indicate the converters (with input format, action and output format specified) and the directed edges (arcs) will connect the converters between each other. The arc from converter A to converter B exists if and only if the output data format and IMT of the converter A is identical as the input data format and IMT of the converter B. Based on that we have the following graph:

With the above graph and the format and IMT of the input data (recognized by one of the recognizers and then validated or given by the end user directly) we may determine the possible conversion paths for the input data. The simplest version of the algorithm to determine possible paths is as follows:

1. Find all the nodes that accept given input data format and IMT.
2. For each found node search for all the paths leading from the node (traverse the processing graph);
3. Found paths (and also their sub-paths) are the conversion possibilities for the given input data format and IMT.

There are some issues that the algorithm (and the EGE user to a certain degree) has to take into account:

- Loops - it is possible that a node has the same input format and output format (e.g. [TEI P5 (text/xml) > TEI P5 (text/xml)]). This may for example indicate a cleaning or restructuring converter.
- Cycles - it is important to be aware of the fact that a cycle may appear, and it cannot (and will not) break the algorithm. For example: [ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml) > ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword)], [ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword) > ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml)]. We assume that there is no sense to use the cycle in the resulting paths, e.g. convert from ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml) to ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword) and then convert back from ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword) to ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml).

- It is possible that there will be two different paths that lead from input format and IMT A to output format and IMT B. In our example there are two paths leading from EAD (text/xml) to ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword): [EAD (text/xml) > ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml)], [ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml) > ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword)] [EAD (text/xml) > MASTER (text/xml)] [MASTER (text/xml) > ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml)] [ENRICH TEI P5 (text/xml) > ENRICH TEI P5 (application/msword)]

6.2 Summary

In the EGE each converter provides a set of conversion actions with specified input and output data, e.g. an action in which converter can use to convert from ENRICH TEI P5 format in text/xml IMT to ENRICH TEI P5 format in application/msword IMT. All conversion actions are connected through their input and output formats and forms convert graph. That representation enables the provision of a mechanism for converting data in a specified format to other another supported format in multiple ways - by searching paths in graph. Paths of conversion can be then be chosen by users through an implemented interface (e.g. GUI or web application forms).

Before converting each input data its IMT may be recognized by Recognizer component. Its format (e.g. ENRICH TEI P5) may then be validated by the Validator component. Alternatively the application which uses EGE may ask the user directly for the input IMT and data format.

7 Overview of the EGE API

The EGE API is a Java based framework that provides basic implementation and interfaces of mechanisms mentioned in the introduction to EGE. The EGE API is written in Java 1.5 (5.0). It directly uses three external libraries:

- JPF ver. 0.12 (<http://jpf.sourceforge.net/>) for plug-in management.
- JUNG ver. 2.0.1-SNAPSHOT (<http://jung.sourceforge.net/>) for conversion graph operations.
- Log4j ver. 1.2.12 (<http://logging.apache.org/log4j/>) for logging.

EGE API contains the following Java packages:

- **pl.psncl.dl.ege** - main package with the implementation of the EGE logic.
- **pl.psncl.dl.ege.component** - contains the interfaces describing the three main EGE components.
- **pl.psncl.dl.ege.exception** - contains the EGE exceptions.
- **pl.psncl.dl.ege.types** - contains the EGE data types used by the components and conversion graph.

7.1 EGE API specific data types (*pl.psncl.dlteam.ege.types*)

Format and MIME type - both are represented as standard String data type. Format represents a name of format, like: ENRICH TEI P5 or EAD. MIME type can be for example: text/xml, application/pdf or application/msword. The values of format and MIME type are not validated in any way. This is intentional, because the internal EGE mechanisms are designed to be very general. If one would like to use the EGE in a context different than the original context connected with the ENRICH project, this should also be possible.

The *pl.psncl.dl.ege.types* includes the following classes:

- **DataType** - contains both format and MIME type information; instances of this class are used to describe both input and output data types in EGE.
- **ConversionAction** - every instance of this class describes one particular conversion operation, which can be performed by specified converter component on concrete input/output data types. A particular converter A can perform conversion of a data in X DataType to Y DataType. The information about X and Y DataTypes is stored in ConversionActionArguments class instance. ConversionAction is also a base object class for a node in conversion graph. Each conversion action can be dynamically configured through properties provided with ConversionActionArguments class instances.
- **ConversionActionArguments** - describes input and output data types for a conversion action. Input and output data types are instances of a DataType class. Each instance provides also arguments for dynamic parameterization of conversion.
- **ConversionsPath** - each instance of this class contains a list (a sequence) of a ConversionAction objects; this list represents path of chained conversion where: input data type from first element of sequence is a source data type and output data type from last element of sequence is a result data type. Adjacent elements of such path have its input/output data types compatible - this is assured during the process of conversion graph construction.

- **ValidationResult** - instances of this class are returned by validation methods. Each instance contains status of validation result (ERROR,SUCCESS or FATAL) and messages.

The UML diagram below shows described relationships between classes.

Each instance of `ConversionsPath` contains sequence of `ConversionAction` instances. `ConversionAction` instance references instance of a class that implements `Converter` interface (loaded by the JPF at EGE start-up) and also specifies conversion action data types (through the instance of the `ConversionActionArguments` class). `ConversionActionArguments` contains information about input and output data types, so each instance of this class references two instances of `DataType` class. `DataType` is an elementary class that contains information about format and MIME type, both kept as `String`.

Conversion process can be dynamically parameterised with properties described within `ConversionActionArguments` instances. `ConversionActionArguments` contains properties definitions written as `String`. Each definition of property should contain at least : unique id of property and its data type. Syntax of properties definitions should be properly described in converter documentation. With documented syntax client application can translate available properties in order to provide e.g. user interface for conversion configuration. Properties configured through default client application interface can be transferred to converter using map argument of `ConversionActionArguments` instance, where : key in map is a unique "id" of property and value is value assigned to property. Validation of properties and default settings should be a converters task.

7.2 Components interfaces

Each component in the EGE (validator, converter or recognizer) can have multiple implementations provided through the extension mechanism of JPF. In order to provide this extensibility in the EGE API the three above interfaces were defined in the `pl.psncl.dl.egc.component` package:

- **Recognizer** - declares major functions of the EGE recognizer, has to be implemented by every external recognizer.
- **Validator** - declares major functions of the EGE validator, has to be implemented by every external validator.
- **Converter** - declares major functions of the EGE converter, has to be implemented by every external converter.
- **ConfigurableConverter** - extends the standard Converter interface with one additional function of `configure()`.

The description of the methods declared in these three interfaces is presented in following sections.

7.3 Recognizer

Recognizers are responsible for the recognition of the MIME type of data. MIME types are media types identifiers registered by IANA (Internet Assigned Number Authority), the EGE however intentionally does not provide any checking mechanism of this standardization. Therefore the MIME types are just instances of the String type.

Declared methods:

- **getRecognizableMimeTypes(): List<String>** - should return a list of MIME types recognized by this recognizer.
- **recognize(InputStream inputData) : String** - for provided input data a particular recognizer implementation tries to recognize the input MIME type and returns it or throws an exception if the input MIME type was not recognized.

7.4 Validator

Validators are responsible for validating the input data with respect to its format, e.g. if sent data is in ENRICH TEI P5 format.

Declared methods:

- **getSupportedValidationTypes() : List<DataType>** - method returns data types that the implemented validator is able to validate.
- **validate(InputStream inputData, DataType inputDataType) : ValidationResult** - method returns instances of the **ValidationResult** type. Every result contains a status (whether the validation ended with success, error or fatal error) and validation messages (about errors or warnings). If **inputDataType** is not supported by Validator implementation, method should throw **ValidatorException**.

7.5 Converter

Converters perform conversion of given input stream and store the result of conversion into the given output stream.

Declared methods:

- **getPossibleConversions() : List<ConversionActionArguments>** - should return list of arguments with pairs of input/output data types supported by the converter implementation and the properties definitions associated with those pairs.
- **convert(InputStream inputData, OutputStream outputData, ConversionActionArguments conversionArguments) : void** - performs conversion of input data contained within given input stream and puts the converted data into the given output stream. Both the expected input data type and the output data type are contained within the conversionArguments parameter and they should be compatible with the particular converter possibilities. With the basic input/output arguments method can receive conversion parameters filled according to the parameters definitions syntax (also contained within the ConversionActionArguments instance).

7.6 ConfigurableConverter

This extends the standard Converter interface with additional configure() method.

Declared methods:

- **configure(Map<String,String> params) : void** - converters that implements this interface can receive additional parameters from JPF plugin descriptor. The method is executed from the EGE configuration manager which translates taken parameters into the map argument. The converter is responsible for reading the map and setting up the configuration. The converter can inform EGE configuration manager about configuration errors by throwing an EGEEException; improperly configured converter will be disconnected from EGE.

7.7 EGE interface and implementation

The main EGE interface is the **pl.psncl.ege.EGE** . It describes functionality for complex and multiple conversions of data. The intention of the EGE is to construct a graph of conversions, where every possibility of conversion is describes by graph paths. The graph structure and its basic algorithms are implemented through external JUNG library by the **EGE framework** class - **pl.psncl.ege.EGEImpl** which is also the main implementation of the EGE interface.

The main methods of **pl.psncl.ege.EGE** interface are:

- **findConversionPaths(DataType sourceDataType) : List<ConversionsPath>** - finds all possible ways of conversion for the given data type; all those ways (conversion paths), are returned as a List of ConversionsPath instances. ConversionsPath instances received from this method can be used as the input parameter of a performConversion() method.
- **findConversionPaths(DataType sourceDataType, DataType resultDataType) : List<ConversionsPath>** - finds all possible ways of conversion from the specified

sourceDataType to resultDataType. Depending on the set of loaded converters, there can be several parallel paths.

- **performConversion(InputStream inputData, OutputStream outputStream, ConversionsPath path) : void** - performs multiple conversions described by the ConversionsPath parameter. Converted input data - provided through the given input stream is written to the output described by the given output stream.
- **performValidation(InputStream inputData, DataType inputDataType) : ValidationResult** - this method performs validation using all loaded through the extension mechanism Validator interface implementations. The method returns ValidationResult instance which contains the status of a result and the validation messages. If no validator recognizes inputDataType as supported then an exception will occur.
- **performRecognition(InputStream inputData) : String** - This method performs the recognition of the MIME type of an input data using all loaded EGE recognizers. If any of the loaded EGE recognizers decodes the MIME type of the input data, the method returns the String value of the MIME type, otherwise the method throws an exception.

The EGE interface methods are implemented by the EGEImpl class of the EGE framework. Internally the conversion graph is initialized in the EGEImpl constructor from the loaded external plugins - implementations of the Converter interface. JPF extensions are managed through an instance of **pl.psncl.dl.egge.EGEConfigurationManager** class. From each loaded converter its supported ConversionActionArguments are read and used for the creation of nodes for the conversion graph. During the graph construction the nodes are connected with the directed edge by rule: an arc from node A to node B can only be added if at least one of the node A output data types is compatible with at least one of the node B input data types. For each compatible input/output pair an arc in the graph is added.

Important Note: EGE API assumes conversion of the data by usage of the streams - one input stream for the input data and one output stream for the output data. In order to make it possible to provide input data and output data consisting of multiple files/directories, EGE implementation requires that every EGE converter accepts data and outputs data by means of a ZIP archive. This requirement is crucial not only for appropriate conversion of data consisting of multiple files/directories, but also for conversion results consisting of multiple files/directories. To have a simple rules for EGE converter creation, EGE implementation requires every converter to obey this requirement. Additionally, for developers' convenience EGE implementation provides functionality for compressing multiple files into a ZIP archive and decompressing ZIP archive. These functions are provided by the ZipIOResolver class. An instance of this class is returned by the *getStandardIOResolver()* method of the *EGEConfigurationManager* instance. Please, note that this requirement is stated by this specific EGE implementation and not by the EGE API itself.

8 Creating EGE extensions

The extension mechanism used in EGE is based on the Java Plugin Framework (JPF). More information about which can be found at: <http://jpf.sourceforge.net> . This section explains how to create sample implementation of a converter.

Currently the EGE project has to offer implementations of extensions :

- [EGE TEI Converter](#) - conversion of TEI format to other formats.
- [EGE XSL Converter](#) - conversion based on XSLT.
- [EGE Validator](#) - validator of XML based formats.

Important: EGE API assumes conversion of the data by usage of the streams - one input stream for the input data and one output stream for the output data. In order to make it possible to provide input data and output data consisting of multiple files/directories, EGE implementation requires that every EGE converter accepts data and outputs data by means of a ZIP archive. This requirement is crucial not only for appropriate conversion of data consisting of multiple files/directories, but also for conversion results consisting of multiple files/directories. To have a simple rules for EGE converter creation, EGE implementation requires every converter to obey this requirement. Additionally, for developers convenience EGE implementation provides functionality for compressing multiple files into a ZIP archive and decompressing ZIP archive. These functions are provided by the `ZipIOResolver` class. An instance of this class is returned by the `getStandardIOResolver()` method of the `EGEConfigurationManager` instance. Please, note that this requirement is stated by this specific EGE implementation and not by the EGE API itself.

8.1.1 Step 1: Java code

Each extension project has to import at least the **EGE API and EGE framework libraries** (**ege-api-X.jar,ege-framework-x.jar where X is the library version**) in order to be able to use the EGE interfaces, data types and extensions mechanism.

In this case the implemented class, named `SampleConverter`, will implement the **`pl.psncl.ege.Converter`** interface. Implementing every method of this interface should result in code that looks like this:

```
package com.myapp.converter;

import java.io.InputStream;
import java.io.OutputStream;

import pl.psncl.ege.component.Converter;
import pl.psncl.ege.exception.ConverterException;
import pl.psncl.ege.types.ConversionActionArguments;
import pl.psncl.ege.types.DataType;

public class SampleConverter implements Converter
{
    public void convert(InputStream input, OutputStream output, ConversionActionArguments
conversionArguments) throws ConverterException, IOException
    {
        // if conversionArguments are correct
        // perform proper conversion:
        // handle properties (if they were defined) taken from conversionArguments
        // read data from input stream
        // transform data according to implemented logic
        // write data into output stream
    }
    public List<ConversionActionArguments> getPossibleConversions()
    {
        // return the list of ConversionActionArguments
        // that describes possibilities
        // of this particular converter implementation.
        return .....;
    }
}
```

Through the **`getPossibleConversions()`** method the converter informs the external application in which it is embedded about the possibilities of the converter. It is done by returning a list of pairs of data types and conversion properties definitions (instances of `ConversionActionArguments`). Method **`convert()`** should contain the necessary conversion logic, which checks the specific `ConversionActionArguments`, handles received parameters, performs conversion on data from the input stream and writes the result of conversion to a given output stream.

IMPORTANT: The input and output streams will be opened and closed by EGE. Therefore the plug-in code should not try to open or close those streams.

Creating converter with input and output data compression.

EGE implementation requires that every EGE converter accepts data and outputs data in form of a ZIP archive. In order to obey this requirement EGE converter may use functions available in the EGE implementation package. These functions are provided by the `ZipIOResolver` class. An instance of this class is returned by the `getStandardIOResolver()` method of the `EGEConfigurationManager` instance. `IOResolver` provides two simple methods for compression and decompression of data :

- `decompressStream(InputStream is, File dir) : void` - unpacks ZIP archive transferred through the given `InputStream` to a target 'dir' folder.
- `compressData(File dir, OutputStream os) : void` - packs specified source 'dir' to a ZIP archive and sends it to the `OutputStream`.

Example code showing the usage of EGE IOResolver is presented below:

```
package com.myapp.converter;

import java.io.InputStream;
import java.io.OutputStream;
import pl.psncl.dl.egc.component.Converter;
import pl.psncl.dl.egc.exception.ConverterException;
import pl.psncl.dl.egc.types.ConversionActionArguments;
import pl.psncl.dl.egc.types.DataType;

public class SampleConverter implements Converter
{
    private final IOResolver ior = EGEConfigurationManager.getInstance().getStandardIOResolver();

    public void convert(InputStream input, OutputStream output, ConversionActionArguments
conversionArguments) throws ConverterException, IOException
    {
        File inputTempDir = new File("in_foobar");
        File outputTempDir = new File("out_foobar");
        try{
            ior.decompressStream(input, inputTempDir); // unpack transferred data into temporary
directory
            // if conversionArguments are correct
            // perform proper conversion:
            // handle properties (if they were defined) taken from conversionArguments
            // read data from temporary directory
            // transform data according to implemented logic
            // write data into output temporary directory
            ior.compressData(outputTempDir, output); // compress converted data from output
temporary directory and transferr it to output stream.
        }finally{
            // cleanup temporary data
        }
    }
    public List<ConversionActionArguments> getPossibleConversions()
    {
        // return the list of ConversionActionArguments
        // that describes possibilities
        // of this particular converter implementation.
        return .....;
    }
}
```

```
}  
}
```

8.1.2 Step 2 : JPF Descriptor

Before creating a .jar file with the plug-in, it is necessary to create the JPF plug-in descriptor to mark the converter class as a JPF plug-in.

Descriptor file name is **plugin.xml** and it should look like this:

```
<?xml version="1.0" ?>  
<!DOCTYPE plugin PUBLIC "-//JPF//Java Plug-in Manifest 0.4"  
"http://jpf.sourceforge.net/plugin_0_7.dtd">  
(1) <plugin id="com.mycompany.converter" version="1.0">  
(2)   <requires>  
(3)     <import plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root"/>  
(4)   </requires>  
(5)   <extension plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root" point-id="Converter" id="SampleConverter">  
(6)     <parameter id="class" value="com.myapp.converter.SampleConverter"/>  
(7)     <parameter id="name" value="Sample Converter"/>  
(8)   </extension>  
(9) </plugin>
```

Every plug-in in JPF has its unique **id** , which is defined in the **plug-in** element by an **id** attribute (in our case it is "**com.mycompany.converter**" , see line 1). Every JPF extension is connected to a specified extension point, which in this case is "**Converter**" (described by a point-id attribute of the extension element in line 5, imported in lines 2 to 4). Extension points are defined within the JPF descriptor of EGE API and they are: Converter, Validator and Recognizer. More information about the JPF plug-in descriptors are available at <http://jpf.sourceforge.net> .

The extension element (lines 5 - 8) contains two additional parameters:

- In line 6 the id "class" and the value containing full name of the class that implements Converter interface, in this example it is "com.myapp.converter.SampleConverter".
- In line 7 the id "name" and value containing the name of the converter.

This descriptor has to be inserted in the root directory of extension .jar file or in its direct sub-directory named "**META-INF**" . Finally to use the created example converter in EGE client application, its .jar file(s) has to be added to the classpath of the EGE client.

8.1.3 Creating other extensions

The process of creating Recognizer and Validator extensions is very similar. First of all we need to create a class that implements one of the chosen interfaces - Recognizer or Validator and secondly change few things in the **plugin.xml** file:

```
<?xml version="1.0" ?>
<!DOCTYPE plugin PUBLIC "-//JPF//Java Plug-in Manifest 0.4"
"http://jpf.sourceforge.net/plugin_0_7.dtd">
(1) <plugin id="com.mycompany.validator" version="1.0">
(2)   <requires>
(3)     <import plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root"/>
(4)   </requires>
(5)   <extension plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root" point-id="Validator" id="SampleValidator">
(6)     <parameter id="class" value="com.myapp.validator.SampleValidator"/>
(7)     <parameter id="name" value="Sample Validator"/>
(8)   </extension>
(9) </plugin>
```

This example shows the extension of Validator. First line shows that the **id** attribute of **plugin** element has changed into different name - every plugin must have a unique name. Line (5) shows the differences within extension element : **point-id** parameter is now of "**Validator**" value and the **id** parameter has changed into '**SampleValidator**' . Finally, it is necessary to change the parameter with id "**class**" in (6) line, where in the attribute value we have to point to our class name - that implements the Validator interface and also change the value attribute of the next parameter - name in line (7). Creating the Recognizer extension is almost the same. The difference is that we need to create the class that implements the Recognizer interface and particular attributes have to be changed in **plugin.xml** :

```
<?xml version="1.0" ?>
<!DOCTYPE plugin PUBLIC "-//JPF//Java Plug-in Manifest 0.4"
"http://jpf.sourceforge.net/plugin_0_7.dtd">
(1) <plugin id="com.mycompany.recognizer" version="1.0">
(2)   <requires>
(3)     <import plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root"/>
(4)   </requires>
(5)   <extension plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root" point-id="Recognizer" id="SampleRecognizer">
(6)     <parameter id="class" value="com.myapp.recognizer.SampleRecognizer"/>
(7)     <parameter id="name" value="Sample Recognizer"/>
(8)   </extension>
(9) </plugin>
```

Once again it is necessary to change the following attributes :

- **id** attribute within the plugin element (line 1);
- **point-id** attribute within the extension element to 'Recognizer' (line 5);
- **id** attribute of the extension element to a unique value which will identify the extension (line 5);
- **value** attribute of both the parameter elements (lines 6-7).

9 XSL converter configuration

9.1 Introduction

The standard EGE API implementation includes two extensions by default:

- **TEI** format converter;
- **XSL** converter.

The XSL converter is able to transform an XML file using a given XSL transformation file. By default there are 2 XSL transformation files defined in the XSL converter plugin descriptor (see below) :

```
<?xml version="1.0" ?>
<!DOCTYPE plugin PUBLIC "-//JPF//Java Plug-in Manifest 0.4"
"http://jpf.sourceforge.net/plugin_0_7.dtd">
<plugin id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.xsl.converter" version="1.0">
  <requires>
    <import plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root"/>
  </requires>
  <extension plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root" point-id="XslConverter"
id="MasterToEnrichConverter">
    <parameter id="class" value="pl.psncl.dl.ege.MultiXslConverter"/>
    <parameter id="name" value="MASTER to Enrich Converter"/>
    <parameter id="xsluri"
value="http://tei.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/XSLT/xsl/master2enrich.xsl"/>
    <parameter id="iMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="iFormat" value="MASTER" />
    <parameter id="oMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="oFormat" value="ENRICH TEI P5" />
  </extension>
  <extension plugin-id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.root" point-id="XslConverter" id="EadToEnrichConverter">
    <parameter id="class" value="pl.psncl.dl.ege.MultiXslConverter"/>
    <parameter id="name" value="EAD to Enrich Converter"/>
    <parameter id="xsluri" value="http://tei.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/XSLT/xsl/ead2enrich.xsl" />
    <parameter id="iMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="iFormat" value="EAD" />
    <parameter id="oMimeType" value="application/zip" />
    <parameter id="oFormat" value="ENRICH TEI P5" />
  </extension>
</plugin>
```

In order to add additional XSL transformations you have to modify the XSL converter plugin descriptor - 'plugin.xml' file located in the META-INF directory of the ege-xsl-converter.jar. To add a new XSL transformation, please follow these 3 steps:

1. Unzip the **ege-xsl-converter.jar**.

2. Modify the '**plugin.xml**' file located in the META-INF directory.
3. Repack the files back to **ege-xsl-converter.jar**.

9.2 *Modifying the 'plugin.xml' descriptor file (adding a new XSL transformation).*

In order to add a new XSL transformation, you have to add a new extension to the 'plugin.xml' descriptor file.

There are 5 required properties of the extension that have to be provided for an XSL transformation :

- **xsluri** where the converter developer can specify URI address of xsl transformation scheme;
- **iMimeType** - defines the mime type of input data;
- **iFormat** - defines the format of input data;
- **oMimeType** - defines the mime type of output data;
- **oFormat** - defines the format of output data.

For instance, in order to add an XSL transformation that transforms data from FOO(text/xml) format to BAR(text/xml) format using foobar.xsl transformation scheme, available under <http://pl.psync.ege.pl/foobar.xsl>, the following definition of an additional extension have to be included into the 'plugin.xml' descriptor file:

```
<extension plugin-id="pl.psync.dl.ege.root" point-id="XslConverter" id="FooToBarConverter">
  <parameter id="class" value="pl.psync.dl.ege.FooToBarConverter"/>
  <parameter id="name" value="FOO to BAR converter"/>
  <parameter id="xsluri" value="http://pl.psync.ege.pl/foobar.xsl" />
  <parameter id="iMimeType" value="text/xml" />
  <parameter id="iFormat" value="FOO" />
  <parameter id="oMimeType" value="text/xml" />
  <parameter id="oFormat" value="BAR" />
</extension>
```

Finally, the '**plugin.xml**' file would look like this:

```
<?xml version="1.0" ?>
<!DOCTYPE plugin PUBLIC "-//JPF//Java Plug-in Manifest 0.4"
"http://jpf.sourceforge.net/plugin_0_7.dtd">
<plugin id="pl.psnec.dl.ege.xsl.converter" version="1.0">
  <requires>
    <import plugin-id="pl.psnec.dl.ege.root"/>
  </requires>
  <extension plugin-id="pl.psnec.dl.ege.root" point-id="XslConverter"
id="MasterToEnrichConverter">
    <parameter id="class" value="pl.psnec.dl.ege.MultiXslConverter"/>
    <parameter id="name" value="MASTER to Enrich Converter"/>
    <parameter id="xsluri"
value="http://tei.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/XSLT/xsl/master2enrich.xsl" />
    <parameter id="iMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="iFormat" value="MASTER" />
    <parameter id="oMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="oFormat" value="ENRICH TEI P5" />
  </extension>
  <extension plugin-id="pl.psnec.dl.ege.root" point-id="XslConverter" id="EadToEnrichConverter">
    <parameter id="class" value="pl.psnec.dl.ege.MultiXslConverter"/>
    <parameter id="name" value="EAD to Enrich Converter"/>
    <parameter id="xsluri" value="http://tei.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/XSLT/xsl/ead2enrich.xsl" />
    <parameter id="iMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="iFormat" value="EAD" />
    <parameter id="oMimeType" value="application/zip" />
    <parameter id="oFormat" value="ENRICH TEI P5" />
  </extension>
  <!-- new FOO to BAR converter plugin declaration -->
  <extension plugin-id="pl.psnec.dl.ege.root" point-id="XslConverter" id="FooToBarConverter">
    <parameter id="class" value="pl.psnec.dl.ege.FooToBarConverter"/>
    <parameter id="name" value="FOO to BAR converter"/>
    <parameter id="xsluri" value="http://pl.psnec.dl.ege.pl/foobar.xsl" />
    <parameter id="iMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="iFormat" value="FOO" />
    <parameter id="oMimeType" value="text/xml" />
    <parameter id="oFormat" value="BAR" />
  </extension>
</plugin>
```

10 EGE Conversion and Validation RESTful Web Service interface

10.1 Introduction

EGE RESTful Web Service is a simple web application which exposes the EGE functionality as a set of RESTful online services.

Assuming that the EGE RESTful Web Service has been installed under 'ege-webapp' name in the application/servlet container, the following URL syntax should be used to perform operations:

```
http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/[resources]
```

The EGE RESTful Web Service supports the following operations (request parameters are specified in the [resources] part):

- **Conversion operations**
 - **List input data types** : http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Conversions/ - lists all the supported input data types.
 - **List conversion paths**: http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Conversions/[input data type] - lists all the possible conversion paths for the given [input data type].
 - **Convert**: http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Conversions/[conversion path] - performs conversion of the given input data according to the given [conversion path].
- **Validation operations**
 - **List input data types** : http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Validation/ - lists all the supported input data types.
 - **Validate**: http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Validation/[input data type] - performs validation of the given input data.

The following sections describe in detail the above operations, in particular the syntax of the [input data type] and the [conversion path] parts.

10.2 Conversion

10.2.1 'List input data types' operation

This operation lists all data types (called input data types) which can be converted by this particular instance of the EGE RESTful Web Service. The operation should be invoked using the GET method of the HTTP protocol. In order to invoke this operation, use the following URL (we assume that the EGE RESTful Web Service is installed under 'ege-webapp' path of the application/servlet container):

```
http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Conversions/
```

where [server_address] is the address of a server on which the EGE RESTful application is running, and the [port] is the port number of the server.

The following responses are possible:

- **status code 200** - when operation has been performed successfully and there are available conversions (there are certain input data types);
- **status code 204** - when no input data types are found - there are no conversions available;
- **status code 405** - 'wrong method' error, when requested URL suggests conversion operation.

For example, for the following request:

```
http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/
```

the following XML response is provided:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<input-data-types xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
  <input-data-type id="TEI,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/" />
  <input-data-type id="MASTER,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/MASTER%3Atext%3Axml/" />
  <input-data-type id="EAD,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/EAD%3Atext%3Axml/" />
</input-data-types>
```

Response data includes a list of nodes describing each supported input data type. The following attributes are available for each input data type:

- **id** - the name of the input data type which should be used in further requests
- **xlink:href** - reference to the EGE RESTful operation - this operation will list all possible conversion paths for this input data type (identified by the 'id' value).

10.2.2 List conversion paths' operation

This operation provides a list of all conversions paths for the specified input data type. This operation is also invoked by the GET method of the HTTP protocol. To obtain a list of conversions paths use the following URL :

```
http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Conversions/[input_data_type]
```

where [input_data_type] is the input data type identifier enclosed in the response of the "list input data types" operation.

Note: the [input_data_type] section of the URL contains code '%3A', which is an encoded ':' - colon sign. Colon sign separates every key part of data type from each other.

For example :

- In URL address - http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/, we can see that [input_data_type] has data type of TEI(text/xml) in a specially encoded format to fit the URI syntax requirements. First part is the format name, which is in our case 'TEI', then we have the first section of the mime type - 'text' and the second section - 'xml'.

The following responses are possible :

- **status code 200** - when the operation has been performed successfully and there exist conversions paths for a given input data type;
- **status code 204** - when no conversions paths are found for a given input data type;
- **status code 405** - 'wrong method' error, when the requested URL suggests "conversion" operation;

For example, for the following request:

```
http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/TEI;text.xml/
```

the following XML could be a response :

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<conversions-paths xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
  <conversions-path xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/TEI%3Aapplication%3Ax-latex/" >
    <path-name><![CDATA[
      l:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/x-latex(TEI Converter)
    ]]></path-name>
    <conversion index="0" >
      <property id="pl.psncl.ege.tei.profileNames">
        <value><![CDATA[default,enrich,iso]]></value>
        <type>array</type>
        <property-name>Profile</property-name>
      </property>
    </conversion>
  </conversions-path>
</conversions-paths>
```

The response contains a list of conversion paths available for a given input data type. Each conversion-path have the following attribute:

- **xlink:href** - reference to EGE RESTful operation of conversion,

and additional sub-nodes :

- **path-name** - which is a name of a conversion path;
- **conversion** - which represents one conversion action (being a part of the conversion path).

Each 'conversion' node (that represents conversion action) contains attribute 'index' - which is a number of the conversion action in sequence of conversions.

Additionally, every 'conversion' node can have one or more sub-nodes named 'property' which describe the possible parameters for a conversion action. Each 'property' node contains an attribute 'id' which identifies the property, and the following sub-nodes:

- **definition** - possible parameters, e.g. accepted property values;
- **type** - data type of the property;
- **property-name** - label of the property.

10.2.3 'Convert' operation.

This operation performs the conversion of a given file using the selected conversion path. This operation can be executed only through the POST method of the HTTP protocol. To perform the conversion of a file the client application has to send the POST request using the URL:

```
http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Conversions/[conversion path]
```

where [conversion path] is a sequence of data types (the first one is the input data type), so

[conversion path]=[input data type]/[data_type_1]/[data_type_2]/.../[data_type_N]/ .

The request has to enclose the file for conversion and the optional request parameter named 'properties' which specifies the properties for concrete conversion actions in the conversion path. The [conversion path] should be understood as a sequence of conversion actions. For instance, the following conversion path:

TEI%3Atext%3Axml/TEI%3Aapplication%3Amsword/

defines one conversion action - conversion of the file in the TEI(text/xml) data type into a file in the TEI(application/msword) data type which is the result of the conversion operation.

Another example :

EAD%3Atext%3Axml/TEI%3Aapplication%3Amsword/TEI%3Aapplication%3Apdf/

defines two conversion actions: the first one converts the EAD(text/xml) input file into a TEI(application/msword) file, the second one converts the resulting TEI(application/msword) file into a TEI(application/pdf) file which is the final result of the conversion operation.

Basically, each pair of data type elements in the conversion path is a conversion action to be performed on the given file.

Optional parameter 'properties' should contain XML data similar to the following:

```
<conversions>
  <conversion index="[position of conversion action]" >
    <property id="[id of property]">
      [assigned value of this property]
    </property>
  </conversion>
</conversions>
```

where every 'conversion' node has the attribute 'index' - which represents the number of the conversion action within the conversion sequence.

Each 'conversion' node can contain sub-nodes named 'property' with the attribute 'id' and the value assigned to it. All possible properties for particular conversion action can be obtained from the "list conversion paths" operation.

For the 'conversion' operation, the following responses are possible:

- **200 status code** - conversion was performed without any problems and converted file was returned;
- **400 status code** - returned when requested conversion path does not exist;
- **405 status code** - 'wrong method' error, when trying to perform conversion operation over GET method of HTTP protocol;

10.3 Example use case.

Let us assume that:

- [server_address] is 'localhost',
- [port] is 8080,

and we want to perform conversion of a file from TEI(text/xml) to TEI(application/msword) format using the default conversion profile.

To achieve our goal we have to :

10.3.1 Step 1 : list of data types

We perform a "list of data types" operation by sending HTTP request with GET method on URL : <http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/> .

In response we receive the following XML data :

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<input-data-types xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
  <input-data-type id="TEI,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/" />
  <input-data-type id="MASTER,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/MASTER%3Atext%3Axml/" />
  <input-data-type id="EAD,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/EAD%3Atext%3Axml/" />
</input-data-types>
```

Please note, that there is one node named 'input-data-type' which matches the input file data type - "TEI(text/xml)".

10.3.2 Step 2 : list conversions paths

- We now have a list of conversion paths for the input data type which matched with our input file data type:

From the previous response we have to select the 'xlink:href' attribute (<http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/>) of the 'TEI,text/xml' input data type and use it to obtain the conversion paths.

In order to receive the list of conversion paths, we perform 'list conversion paths' operation of the EGE RESTful Web Service by sending HTTP request with GET method on the extracted URL : <http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/>.

10.3.3 Step 3 : handling "list of conversions paths" response.

In the response we will receive the following XML data :

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<conversions-paths xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
  <conversions-path xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/TEI%3AApplication%3Amsword/" >
  <path-name><![CDATA[
    I:TEI,text/xml/O:TEI,application/msword(TEI Converter)
  ]]></path-name>
  <conversion index="0" >
    <property id="pl.psnc.dl.ege.tei.profileNames">
      <definition><![CDATA[default,enrich,iso, ]]></definition>
      <type>array</type>
      <property-name>Profile</property-name>
    </property>
  </conversion>
</conversions-path>
</conversions-paths>
```

XML contains only one conversion path, represented by 'conversions-path' node that gives us the possibility to perform conversion from TEI(text/xml) format to TEI(application/msword) format.

10.3.4 Step 4 : setting conversion properties.

XML response returned by the "list conversions paths" operation contains a list of conversions. In the above case there is only one conversion node. Each conversion node defines the properties for the conversion action it represents. In our example we have the 'pl.psncl.dl.ege.tei.profileNames' property with three possible values : default, enrich and iso. We will use 'default' value for the 'pl.psncl.dl.ege.tei.profileNames' parameter by setting the 'properties' parameter (for the 'convert' operation) to the following value:

```
<conversions>
  <conversion index="0" >
    <property id="pl.psncl.dl.ege.tei.profileNames">
      default
    </property>
  </conversion>
</conversions>
```

10.3.5 Step 5 : performing conversion.

We have to perform POST request on the the following URL:
<http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Conversions/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/TEI%3Aapplication%3Amsword/> , with a filled request parameter 'properties' and an input file to convert.

As a result we will receive the converted file (in the TEI(application/msword) format - '.docx' extension).

10.4 Validation

10.4.1 'List input data types' operation

This operation lists all the data types which can be validated by EGE RESTful Web Service. The operation should be invoked using the GET method of the HTTP protocol. In order to invoke this operation, use the following URL (we assume that the EGE RESTful Web Service is installed under 'ege-webapp' path of the application/servlet container):

- **http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Validation/**

where [server_address] is the address of a server on which the EGE RESTful application is running, and the [port] is the port number of the server.

The following responses are possible:

- **status code 200** - when operation has been performed successfully and there are available data types for validation;
- **status code 204** - when there is no supported data types;
- **status code 405** - 'wrong method' error, when requested URL suggests validation operation.

For example, for the following request:

- **http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Validation/**

the following XML is received as a response:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<validations xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
  <input-data-type id="TEI,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Validation/TEI%3Atext%3Axml/" />
  <input-data-type id="MASTER,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Validation/MASTER%3Atext%3Axml/" />
  <input-data-type id="EAD,text/xml" xlink:href="http://localhost:8080/ege-
webapp/Validation/EAD%3Atext%3Axml/" />
</validations>
```

The response data includes a list of nodes describing each supported data type. The following attributes are available for each data type:

- **id** - the name of the data type which should be used in further requests;
- **xlink:href** - reference to the operation of validation.

10.4.2 'Validation' operation

This operation performs the validation of a given file using the selected conversion data type. This operation can only be executed through the POST method of the HTTP protocol. To perform the validation of a file the client application has to send the POST request using the URL:

```
http://[server_address]:[port]/ege-webapp/Validation/[input data type]
```

where [input_data_type] is the input data type identifier enclosed in the response of the "list input data types" operation.

The request has to enclose the file for validation.

For the 'conversion' operation, the following responses are possible :

- **200 status code** - validation was performed without any problems and response XML was returned;
- **400 status code** - returned when either request was formed improperly or provided data type is not supported by any of the EGE validators;

With code '200' of result client application receives validation result encoded in XML format.

For example, for the following request:

- **http://localhost:8080/ege-webapp/Validation/EAD%3Atext%3Axml**

the following XML response is provided:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
  <validation-result>
    <status>ERROR</status>
    <messages>
      <message>
        <![CDATA[
          1) Error in line (3), column (8) : Document root element "TEI.2", must match
          DOCTYPE root "ead".
        ]]>
      </message>
    </messages>
  </validation-result>
```

Response data contains one "validation-result" section with :

- **status** - which may take one of three values : ERROR - when validator found some errors, SUCCESS - when no errors were found (warnings possible), FATAL - when fatal errors occurred;
- **messages** - which contains multiple "message" sections, each with text values : error or warning messages.

10.5 Error response

During any operation an unexpected error may occur which will result in 500 status code of HTTP response, in that case application should also return xml data:

```
<?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
<error msg="sample error message" exclass="com.my.SampleException">part of stack trace</error>
```

The response contains only one 'error' element with part of a stack trace as content and with the following attributes :

- **msg** - which contains the exception message;
- **exclass** - which contains the exception class.

11 Download

The EGE web package is available for download at:

<http://dl.psnc.pl/software/EGE/download.html>

Earlier versions of the EGE are also made available there as well.

12 Installing and configuring EGE web package

12.1 Installing the EGE

1. Download the Servlet/JSP container Apache Tomcat (version 5.5 and 6.x supported) from this page - [Apache Tomcat](#) and install it. Or install it through another method depending upon your operating system.
2. Unzip the downloaded **ege-webapp.zip** . Copy both "ege-webservice" and "ege-webclient" directories into the '*APACHE_TOCMAT_HOME/webapps/*' folder.
3. Configure the EGE web client - instructions can be found at : [Download the EGE web client](#)
4. Start Apache Tomcat from command line by typing '**startup**' from the '*APACHE_TOMCAT_HOME/bin/*' folder.
5. Run the EGE RESTful client application in your browser by going to the following URL: `http://localhost:[port]/ege-webclient/`, where [port] is your configured tomcat HTTP port (8080 by default).

12.2 Configuring of the EGE

Before starting EGE web client it is necessary to configure URL address of EGE RESTful web service in web.xml.

web.xml file can be found in /WEB-INF folder of EGE web client project. There is XML entry in configuration :

```
<context-param>
  <description>
    EGE RESTful web service URL.
  </description>
  <param-name>webservice.url</param-name>
  <param-value>http://localhost:8080/ege-webservice/</param-value>
</context-param>
```

Address to web service is specified inside **param-value** entity. By default there is "`http://localhost:8080/ege-webservice/`".

Important: EGE web client extensively uses AJAX requests and therefore it has to be run over the same domain as EGE RESTful web service.

13 EGE Case Studies and Testing

The EGE conversions were initially tested with the same testbed of MASTER and EAD samples that were used in the investigation of the development and validation of migration tools as case studies. See <http://tei.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/Migration/index.xml> for more information on these migration case studies.

The *Manuscript Access through Standards for Electronic Records* (MASTER) was an EU project funded to create a single XML-based standard for computer-readable descriptions of manuscripts. In many ways this project was the pre-cursor to ENRICH. The MASTER data format was updated and modified and eventually incorporated as a module into the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) P5 Guidelines. MASTER itself was based on an earlier (P4) version of the Guidelines. The TEI P5 module has since evolved further and in turn has been used as the basis of the ENRICH specification. The ENRICH project has contributed its resolutions on the creation of manuscript descriptions back to the TEI and they have been ratified by the TEI Technical Council and adopted back into their Guidelines. Owing to the history of relationship between MASTER, TEI, and ENRICH, it was an obvious candidate for a case study on the development of migration tools. Since the development of transformation stylesheets for that investigation into migration tools (ENRICH D3.3), these stylesheets were included in the EGE default setup.

The test bed of MASTER files included some from the following :

1. **AMI:** [About 500 full records relating to Icelandic manuscripts](#) created by the [Stofnun Árna Magnússonar](#) (Arní Magnússon Institute) in Reykjavik
2. **BMR:** [About 30 full records](#) from the [Manuscritos de América en las Colecciones Reales](#)(American manuscripts in the Royal Collections) portal created at the University of Alicante
3. **IRHT:** [About 350 short records relating to French manuscripts](#), extracted from the Médium database maintained at the [Institut de Recherche et de l'Histoire des Textes](#), Paris
4. **KB:** [About 90 records relating to Dutch and Flemish mediaeval manuscripts](#), from the collections of the [Koninklijke Bibliotheek](#) (Royal Library), The Hague
5. **NLP:** [About 50 records relating to mediaeval manuscripts](#) in the collections of the [Národní knihovna České republiky \(Czech National Library\)](#), Prague
6. **Well:** a small collection from [The Wellcome Trust](#)

In addition, the previous investigation had also tested Encoded Archival Description (EAD) as a format. EAD is a set of guidelines describing the intellectual and physical aspects of archival finding aids so that the information they contain may be easily searched, retrieved, displayed, and exchanged in a predictable platform-independent manner. It was produced by the Society of American Archivists and the Library of Congress. Many of the EAD concepts are based upon early work with the TEI and there is a large crossover of users between EAD and TEI. EAD is sometimes preferred for archival collection metadata and TEI is generally preferred for textual content, though increasingly TEI is becoming a de facto standard. The EAD format used by the Bodleian Library, University of Oxford, is based on version 1.0 of the standard. This was then superseded by a second version of the EAD standard in 2002.

No successive versions of the EAD standards have since been released, though it is still used in many libraries.

The files provided by the Bodleian for this included:

- [additional-a.xml](#) (Additional A Manuscripts)
- [additional-b.xml](#) (Additional B Manuscripts)
- [barlow.xml](#) (The Barlow Manuscripts)
- [don.xml](#) (MSS Don., Donations)
- The input files to the conversion as a whole are available at:
<http://tei.oucs.ox.ac.uk/ENRICH/XSLT/testbed/EAD/>

The EGE also provides conversions to/from MS Word's DOCX format (sometimes misleadingly called the 'Office Open' format), and to/from the standard TEI format. These have been tested with a number of documents, some containing manuscript descriptions and the results are impressive. However, there is certainly room for further development and improvement in this area.

14 Conclusions and Recommendations

The ENRICH Garage Engine as a RESTful Web Service with user-friendly web front-end is a good demonstrator of the development of useful service in a distributed 'web of data' method. It far outstrips the original task that it replaces and offers great scope for future development. Further development and maintenance is not funded as part of the ENRICH project, but it is hoped that it will be further developed in future funding bids. It provides an extremely good starting point for future work in format migration in service-oriented architectures.

This report would like to make the following five recommendations:

1. The stylesheets used for transformations in the EGE are sufficient for their usage in the ENRICH project. However, for greater use by other projects additional development should be encouraged of these transformations including further development for additional use cases and greater documentation on the extensibility and customisation of the underlying stylesheets. It is recommended that any additional development work in format migration and conversion be used to improve the existing EGE solution.
2. Increased development should also be considered for new stylesheets for additional formats (such as MARC) since the addition of a single new stylesheet then plugs into the EGE to allow a number of news transformation paths. It is recommended that where new format migration and conversion stylesheets are being developed for future projects, that these do so in a manner compatible with the EGE framework so that they may hopefully be incorporated into it.
3. The EGE is a coordinated RESTful web service framework that uses a documented API for interaction. Projects producing web-based software should use approaches that allow access to such APIs for building services on them, here demonstrated by the ENRICH EGE Web Client. Linking together of these individual web services to a greater whole is a roadmap for richer and more robust web applications. It is recommended that projects developing web-based software should produce a RESTful web service API and build and front-end systems on top of this.
4. The EGE is an open extensible system which one is able to customise to individual project needs. It is also open source, released under the GPL version 3 licence. Where possible it is recommended that software be open source and built in a manner that encourages extended and improving that software.
5. TEI P5 XML, here used as the ENRICH TEI P5 Specification, is not only a good format for the representation of textual materials and metadata, but is also sufficient as an intermediate format in a conversion pathway between two disparate formats. TEI P5 XML is recommended for any similar endeavours undertaken at a later date.

Part 2:

Report on Best Practice in Handling of Unicode and Non-Unicode Data

1 Executive Summary

The use of Unicode is rightly commonplace as a character encoding for electronic documents. While the choice to use Unicode is beneficial, there are many contexts in which there are valid needs for characters and glyphs not represented in Unicode. Any project using non-standard characters should document needed information about these characters and their use. The nature of medieval manuscripts and their descriptions, upon which the ENRICH project is founded, means that the ENRICH project is more likely than non-medieval projects to have need of non-standard characters. In addition, large European projects working in an internationalized context not only need to use Unicode, but document carefully any time they depart from it and provide appropriate fallbacks for rendering and presentation. The ENRICH project uses the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) P5 Guidelines recommendations on XML markup methods to record and document any non-Unicode characters or individual glyphs of interest to those creating an electronic resource. As a project ENRICH fully endorses and benefits from both Unicode and the TEI recommendations.

This report provides an introduction to character encoding which surveys the terminology and key concepts needed to understand the remaining discussion, the use of Unicode and non-Unicode characters in XML, and the normalization and standardization of non-standard characters. In addition the representation of non-standard characters both for markup and annotation are discussed before a final section on the use of Unicode in the ENRICH project and the ENRICH gBank web frontend and web service API as developed. The development of the gBank is an added benefit to the method chosen by the ENRICH project and forms an additional software deliverable in its own right.

There are a number of clear recommendations that come out of the use of Unicode and non-standard characters in the ENRICH project.

- Wherever possible projects should use a Unicode character encoding such as UTF-8.
- Projects needing to reference or record non-standard characters should in preference adopt a system such as the TEI Gaiji module recommendations for documenting their use of non-standard characters and/or the Unicode Private Use Area. ENRICH strongly recommends use of the TEI Guidelines in preference for such undertakings.
- Character normalization should be well-documented and consistently applied using standardized decomposed characters that have wide font support. Any mappings to such characters need to be clearly documented.
- All transformations, migrations, indexing and search routines should use the same table of equivalences in searching for normalized fonts.
- Although CSS3 web fonts provide a promising method to push fonts to users viewing a web page, this should not yet be recommended practice until consistently implemented across browsers.

2 Introduction

In any electronic document the agreements by which the characters are encoded are simultaneously of critical importance and often glossed over in vague mentions or now more frequently that "we'll just use Unicode" without a proper understanding of the implications and limitations of this decision. The choice to use Unicode is a good one, but especially in the context of medieval manuscripts descriptions may impose limitations on the recording of certain characters. This is especially the case with respect to large European projects working in an internationalized context.

To counter any such limitations, the Text Encoding Initiative (TEI) P5 Guidelines have developed mark-up methods to record and document any non-Unicode characters or individual glyphs of interest to those creating the electronic resource. As a project ENRICH fully endorses and benefits from Unicode and the TEI recommendations.

This report provides an introduction to character encoding which surveys the terminology and key concepts needed to understand the remaining discussion, the use of Unicode and non-Unicode characters in XML, and the normalization and standardization of non-standard characters. In addition the representation of non-standard characters both for markup and annotation are discussed before a final section on the use of Unicode in the ENRICH project and the ENRICH gBank web frontend and web service API as developed. The conclusion contains a number of recommendations for best practice in this area.

3 Character Sets and Encoding

The basis of electronic documents is the representation of one thing by another in a consistent systematic manner, hopefully also in accordance with internationally recognised standards and recommendations. At the very base of such recommendations is the application to the smallest distinctive units in any particular writing system (e.g. characters or ideograms). The development of character sets and the problems which surround these are partly related to the historical development of technological representations of these characters and also the identification, manipulation, and rendering of any characters of a natural language. Partly as an attempt to overcome many of these problems, the Unicode Standard (ISO 10646) attempts to enable the consistent representation and manipulation of text in the majority of the world's existing and historical writing systems.

3.1 Terminology and Key Concepts

In order to understand any of the issues surrounding character encoding, XML's use of Unicode, and the markup of non-standard characters, it is necessary to introduce some key concepts and especially the terminology that relates to them. The term 'character' is a good example as its use is wide and extremely varied in meaning. It can simultaneously refer to the visible symbol on the page and also to the letter or ideograph represented by that symbol. And yet, these two aspects of a 'character' are important to keep distinct when discussing their representation in electronic form. A single 'character' may have multiple forms of representation. For example, the letter 'a' may appear as a single compartment or have a double-compartment where the top ascender curls over. In the following figure a number a

different 'a' characters are rendered with different fonts and thus appear different even though we recognise them all as the same abstract 'character' in one sense, they are represented by different physical forms or 'glyphs' in particular textual instantiations.

An uppercase 'A' would be a different character and represented by a different set of glyphs. However, it is important to note that in one case above, with the 'Capitals Regular' font, the lowercase letter 'a' glyph has the appearance of a typical glyph for an uppercase 'A' character. This distinction, between abstract characters as concepts and their instantiations as glyphs is fundamental to any discussion of electronic documents and their character encodings.

A collection of these abstract characters that are suitable for the representation of documents created in a particular writing system is termed a 'character set'. A document's character set is simply this collection of abstract characters, but the character set that a computer program or processing device knows how to deal with is a set of abstract characters which have been predefined to match a set of numbers or 'code points' through which the characters are represented internally to the underlying machine. This is a 'coded character set' because each of these abstract characters is given a unique processable code. A writing system is a particular script used to express an particular language through the use of a defined character set. (In addition writing systems usually also have understood rules and generally are representations of at least one spoken language.)

Historically many different competing character sets have been created and the plethora of these caused much work in translating from one to another. The development of Unicode is an

attempt to rationalise these all into a single form of coded character sets and actively maintain and develop it through a public international consortium. In the Unicode standard, each abstract character is given a definition and assigned a unique code point. Unicode differs from earlier attempts at coded character sets partly by its current size and scope, the in-built provision for near limitless expansion, and importantly the increasing provision by commercial providers (in fonts, hardware and software) to support each new release of the standard.

3.2 Unicode and XML

One of the important aspects of the XML standard is that it only requires that Unicode be supported internally by any XML processing system. This means that all abstract characters (not including markup) in an XML document must be treated as if they are in Unicode for purposes of internal parsing of the document. In practice many character encoding systems are used, but in most cases these are translated to one of the Unicode character sets (e.g. UTF-8 or UTF-16) by the processor before it undertakes to process it. Such transformations (as long as the character encoding used is properly declared) are mostly invisible to users. However, in the case of ENRICH, Unicode UTF-8 should be seen as the recommended character encoding to use.

Characters in Unicode texts can be entered in a number of ways. These include both entering the character directly (if the software and font manufacturers have provided a method to do so) or representing the character with the appropriate 'Numeric Character Reference' (NCR). If the character is able to be entered directly in a system that gives an appropriate rendering of them, then this is to be preferred. Otherwise using an NCR might be necessary. These take the form of '&#D;' where 'D' is an integer representing the code point of the abstract character in base 10, or '&#H;' where 'H' is the same code point but expressed in hexadecimal notation, both delimited by the ampersand and semicolon. Generally the hexadecimal form is to be preferred since this is easier to relate to the code point. For example the lowercase 'thorn' character common in Middle English texts might be directly entered as 'þ', entered as a decimal NCR as 'þ' or hexadecimal NCR as 'þ'. This notation does not need special declaration or explanation to the XML processor, as all XML processor should be able to recognise NCRs and replace them with the required code point. This means that any Unicode character that is not able to be represented by the hardware or software has a method of entry. However, it is fairly unreadable by humans. DTD-based XML documents have a third option, that of declaring a named character entity with a replacement at the head of their document. These give a standard way for that character entity to be referred to in that one document.

3.3 Non-Unicode Characters and XML

Although Unicode attempts to be comprehensive there are instances of characters which are not included in the Unicode standard. In some cases this is because these characters have not been demonstrated to merit the status of an individual abstract character rather than a combination of two or more existing characters. When a character can be composed of the existing Unicode characters and a number of combining characters, then that is usually considered the preferred route. However, if the character has different semantics than those implied by use of the existing and similarly looking characters, that might help qualify it for inclusion. That said, Unicode included many compromise or compatibility characters to begin

with because of their historical existence in common character sets and their support by hardware and software manufacturers.

One of the most important aspects of Unicode character encoding is that it reserves over 137000 character code points for private use. These characters are in the 'Private Use Area' (PUA) code point range from U+E000 to U+F8FF (though U+F0000 to U+FFFFD and U+100000 to U+10FFFFD are reserved as well, they are less frequently used). The Unicode Consortium has agreed never to assign characters in these ranges which means that they are free for use by individual projects, organizations, or commercial interests. There is no guarantee, however, that your PUA characters will not conflict with those chosen by others. Hence, it is best if PUA characters are either solely used internally or provided with some mechanism for normalization to an existing Unicode character.

3.4 Normalization and Standardization

The ENRICH project believes that it is necessary for every Unicode-based project dealing with any unusual characters to agree on, consistently implement and document a comprehensive and coherent normalization practice. This is necessary not only for proper long-term preservation and data migration, but also for interoperation of resources.

Unicode has two different types of code points. These are characters which are precomposed single code points or those that are code point sequences of a base character with one or more combining characters such as diacritics. Scripts more recently added to Unicode usually do not have this code-point duplication because Unicode attempts to introduce no new precomposed characters that could be created by the use of combining characters. Nonetheless there are numerous duplications that exist in the older or comparability layers of the character set.

For the ENRICH gBank, as discussed later, a straightforward normalization and standardization method of providing alternative basic ASCII characters was implemented. The exceptions to this are those characters which do not have acceptable equivalents in basic ASCII. In addition because of the access to the gBank as a web service, any individual project can choose to override these normalizations at any point on a character-by-character basis. ENRICH normalization decomposes ligatures and attempts to choose the lowest common denominator canonical characters that are the closest semantic equivalents to the non-Unicode abstract character.

4 Representation of Non-Standard Characters

The ENRICH project recommends the methods described in the TEI Guidelines for the [Representation of Non-standard Characters and Glyphs](#). This method allows for the markup of individual non-standard characters in any level of textual transcription or metadata, while also recording additional details concerning that character. The ENRICH gBank concentrates on characters rather than glyphs but the same methods can be used for analysis of glyphs by using a <glyph> element rather than the <char> element discussed below. There are two basic aspects to the representation of non-standard characters in ENRICH documents. These are the markup constructs that exist for the representation of information concerning those characters, and the annotation or markup of the characters themselves.

4.1 Descriptive Information for Non-Standard Characters

If a document is using a Unicode character encoding, then the properties of that character are known to the text processing systems through various character encoding libraries. If the document includes non-standard characters, perhaps encoded using the Unicode PUA, then this information is not available and recommended practice is to provide it through some form of additional markup. The TEI provides a method to do this using its `<charDecl>` element which provides a container in the document's metadata for `<char>` (or `<glyph>`) elements. Each of these `<char>` elements may in turn contain a variety of elements to represent various properties of characters, including:

- `<charName>`
(character name) contains the name of a character, expressed following Unicode conventions.
- `<desc>`
(description) contains a brief description of the object documented by its parent element, including its intended usage, purpose, or application where this is appropriate.
- `<gloss>`
identifies a phrase or word used to provide a gloss or definition for some other word or phrase.
- `<charProp>`
(character property) provides a name and value for some property of the parent character or glyph.
- `<mapping>`
(character mapping) contains one or more characters which are related to the parent character or glyph in some respect, as specified by the type attribute.
- `<graphic/>`
indicates the location of an inline graphic, illustration, or figure (to act as a surrogate of the character).
- `<note>`
contains a note or annotation

Inside the `<charProp>` element one is allowed three elements:

- `<unicodeName>`
(unicode property name) contains the name of a registered Unicode normative or informative property.
- `<localName>`
(locally-defined property name) contains a locally defined name for some property.
- `<value>`
(value) contains a single value for some property, attribute, or other analysis.

If the property is a 'Unicode Normative Property', then it is mandatory to have a `<unicodeName>` element. Otherwise, its name must be specified by means of a `<localName>` element. An example of such a char element might be:

```
<char xml:id="efa4">
  <desc>LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A INSULAR F</desc>
  <charProp>
    <localName>entity</localName>
    <value>afinslig</value>
  </charProp>
  <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="Unicode">□</mapping>
  <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="PUA">U+EFA4</mapping>
  <mapping type="standardized">af</mapping>
  <graphic url="images/efa4.png"/>
</char>
```

Here a `<char>` element is given as an example from the ENRICH gBank and all entries in the gBank have at least these elements. It has an `xml:id` attribute that is unique in the document.

In the case of the ENRICH gBank the values for these are xml:id attributes are lowercase unicode PUA code point values. In the ENRICH gBank <desc> is used instead of <charName> because in the case of combined characters (suggestions for precomposed characters made from a number of combining characters) we have multiple descriptions and under the TEI schema a character is sensibly only allowed to have one <charName>.

A <charProp> element provides the <localName> and <value> for a property of the character. In this case it is the entity name chosen for it by the Medieval Unicode Font Initiative (MUFI). The mappings provided by MUFI are also provided with <mapping> elements. <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="Unicode"> provides a use of the Unicode PUA code point. If one does not have a MUFI-compatible font installed (such as Andron Web Scriptor), then this character will not display properly. The <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="PUA"> element provides a Unicode-style text representation of the Unicode PUA code point used. <mapping type="standardized"> provides a standardized basic ASCII canonical normalization for these characters. So in this case a small ligature between an 'a' and an insular 'f' has been normalized as the decomposed characters 'a' and 'f'. The <graphic/> element provides the URL of a graphic image that is representative of, or a surrogate for, the character.

4.2 Annotation of Non-Standard Characters

For the construction of the ENRICH gBank, a set of <charDecl> elements containing <char> elements such as those above, the metadata provided in these <char> elements is sufficient. However, this metadata needs to be used in the manuscript descriptions and where extant textual transcriptions in ENRICH. In these cases the TEI recommendations have a globally-available element <g> from which one is able to reference the <char> elements either within the same document if a project has provided its own <char> elements, or directly from the gBank itself. In an (entirely hypothetical) document this might appear as any of the following:

7. So eld and hue hit hadde <g ref="#efa4"/>eynted and forebete
8. So eld and hue hit hadde <g ref="#efa4">af</g>eynted and forebete
9. So eld and hue hit hadde <g ref="http://beta.manuscriptorium.com/apps/gbank/char.php?id=efa4"/>eynted and forebete
10. So eld and hue hit hadde <g ref="http://beta.manuscriptorium.com/apps/gbank/char.php?id=efa4">af</g>eynted and forebete

In the first and third of these examples the <g/> is provided as an empty element referencing either a local or remote copy of this character's <char> element. In second and fourth examples although it still references a local or remote copy of the description it also provides a transliteration of the character for fall-back display. Either of these methods is deemed acceptable.

5 The ENRICH Project and Non-Standard Characters

ENRICH has done its best to adhere to recommended Unicode practice and use Unicode character sets internally for its work. As most projects use Unicode whenever possible these days, to do otherwise is not best practice and may indicate work that is unlikely to be funded. However, there are many completely valid instances where for using characters that do not appear yet in Unicode or will never appear in Unicode because they go against Unicode principles. For example, precomposed characters of convenience used when studying a specific scribal variance. The ENRICH recommendation is to use TEI methods of description of these characters to preserve information about their standardization and reasons for use.

5.1 The ENRICH gBank and the Medieval Unicode Font Initiative

To provide a usable service for the ENRICH project, and potentially the others, the project decided in its investigation of Unicode to create a gBank. This is named both for the <g> elements which might reference these character descriptions, but also the TEI's **Gaiji** module for non-standard characters which contains these elements.

The ENRICH Gaiji Bank has obviously benefited from the [TEI P5 Guidelines](#) upon which it is based. But less obvious is that the initial definitions have come from the [Medieval Unicode Font Initiative](#) and the work of Odd Einar Haugen, Andreas Stötzner, Alec McAllister amongst many others. The graphic files that accompany every character description are generated from the MUFI-compliant version 3 of Andreas Stötzner's [Andron Scriptor Web font](#).

5.2 ENRICH gBank in the Manuscriptorium System

There are five applications of gBank in the ENRICH Manuscriptorium system. Each provides different service in order to enable both end-users and content authors to work efficiently with documents that require usage of special characters and glyphs, often not supported by Unicode.

The gBank is used:

- as a database for the newly created standalone gBank end-user interface
- as a database for the newly created standalone gBank API interface
- to internally enhance indexing routines and the search and retrieval system
- to enhance the presentation layer through display of the characters covered by gBank
- to enhance searching texts that originated without using gBank and Gaiji module

5.3 gBank End-User Interface

The standalone online application is now available for use at <http://beta.manuscriptorium.com/apps/gbank>. The application presents the content of the gBank database to end-users interested in finding a particular non-standard character. The user friendly interface displays characters ordered into sets, which can be further searched in order to find individual characters. As there are images available (for almost all of the characters) it is fairly straightforward to find a particular character. If an image is not available, a short description is displayed as a label.

ENRICH gBank - version 0.92 - Mozilla Firefox
 http://localhost/gbank/table.php#dirName0

gBANK
 The ENRICH GalJI Bank

Edition: draft; First Draft: 19.10.2009
 Authority: Oxford University Computing Services
 Distributor: ENRICH Project

(a) Structural ligatures
 (b) Non-structural ligatures
 Subrange 2: Small capitals
 Subrange 3: Enlarged minuscules
 Subrange 4: Base-line abbreviation characters
Subrange 5: Modified base-line abbreviation characters

h	h̄	k	k̄	q	q̄	ŕ	r̄	ſ
ſ̄	v	x	x̄	þ	þ̄	þ̂	þ̃	

Subrange 6: Combining marks
 Subrange 7: Combining superscript characters
 Subrange 8: Punctuation marks

Hotovo

The user can display a particular character description by clicking on the appropriate image. For end-users' convenience a valid XML code is displayed - this code can be copied and pasted directly in the XML metadata of the particular digital document.

The `<g>` element then fully substitutes the special character, the original information is transferred into the XML records without any information loss.

```
<titleStmt> <title>A sample title with a special <g ref="#eec6"/> character</title> </titleStmt>
```

The subsequent processing of the information represented by the `<g>` element is ensured for instance by the gBank API interface.

5.4 gBank API Interface

The gBank API interface performs one important task: it returns properties of a selected characters based on request passing character's ID. The format of the request is as follows:

<http://beta.manuscriptorium.com/apps/gbank/char.php?id=eec6>

The value of id parameter identifies the particular character. The API then returns the full character description as seen below:

```
<char xml:id="eec6">
  <desc>LATIN SMALL LIGATURE D ROTUNDA D ROTUNDA</desc>
  <charProp>
    <localName>entity</localName>
    <value>drotrotlig</value>
  </charProp>
  <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="Unicode">□</mapping>
  <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="PUA">U+EEC6</mapping>
  <mapping type="standardized">dd</mapping>
  <graphic url="images/eec6.png"/>
</char>
```

Any application processing or retrieving the information can then again substitute the <g> elements with an appropriate information available in the <char> element (e.g. use the graphic, alternate mappings etc.)

5.5 Indexing and Searching with the gBank

5.5.1 Indexing with gBank Characters

The gBank database is also used during indexing routines within the ENRICH Manuscriptorium system. The metadata in ENRICH Manuscriptorium is indexed into a special database which enables efficient on-line searching. As it is difficult to include the non-Unicode characters into the search database, the gBank is used to substitute the <g> element with the standard mappings. For instance supposing we have following information for LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A F:


```
<char xml:id="eg-efa3">
  <desc>LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AF</desc>
  <charProp>
    <localName>entity</localName>
    <value>af lig</value>
  </charProp>
  <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="Unicode">□</mapping>
  <mapping type="MUFI" subtype="PUA">U+EFA3</mapping>
  <mapping type="standardized">af</mapping>
  <graphic url="images/efa3.png"/>
</char>
```

We can then use the standardized mapping and replace the character **af** with 'af' in the indexes.

5.5.2 Searching with gBank Characters

Users can do the same when they build their search query: they can simply use the standardized character mappings instead of the original character. This approach is very important for end-users, because majority of the special characters - or even those covered by Unicode - are difficult to enter into search queries using common keyboards and fonts.

Therefore as a result of our analysis and tests we provide standardized mappings to basic ASCII for each character in the gBank suite, using the principle that they should be able to be

easily typed by a common keyboard and are covered all common fonts. The only exceptions to these are the medieval thorn 'þ' and eth 'ð' characters which are included because there are no easy basic ASCII transliteration and as they were present in extended ASCII they are present in most fonts. In all standardization any ligatures have been decomposed into their component parts and any combining non-alphabetic modifiers (accents, etc.) have been removed. All combining alphabetic characters have been decomposed as separate characters.

For instance considering the example above: having **ƒ** with 'af' standardized mappings then the user can simply enter 'abc**af**def' string into the query line and as a result not only abc**af**def will be found, but also the 'abc**ƒ** def' will be found too. Of course, the search result would be wider if using this approach, but the number of overabundant records will not be significant because of the limited size of the gBank database.

These features are implemented into ENRICH Manuscriptorium, but have not yet been extensively tested with real world examples.

5.5.3 Advanced Search Features Using gBank Characters

There are many metadata sources that do not use TEI P5 to create their primary metadata. Therefore they do not use the <g>element within their markup or provide descriptions as <char> elements (e.g. MARC, or other format sources including those retroconverted from print sources). However, even for these sources the gBank suite can be used to make search tasks more efficient. In most cases these sources use their own standardized mappings to transcribe special characters not available on a standard keyboard. When aggregating documents from a particular source its mappings can be analyzed and their individual standardized mappings can be linked with gBank standardized mappings. This way a table of equivalences in variation can be created and placed within the search system. This has already been implemented and is in use in the ENRICH Manuscriptorium system.

As a result of this work all end-users querying the ENRICH Manuscriptorium using gBank standardized character mappings will be able to retrieve documents from sources using different mapping approaches (and vice versa).

5.5.4 Support of gBank in the Presentation Layer

The final but significant task when implementing gBank into Manuscriptorium was to analyze and prepare the rendering and presentation of texts and descriptions within the end-users interface.

5.5.5 Use of Images and Standardized Mappings

The system again uses the incorporated gBank database and replaces the <g> element either with an image (preferred) or standard mappings (where images are not available). So the user can read the information in the most natural and comfortable way. This approach is implemented and working in the ENRICH Manuscriptorium system.

5.5.6 Use of TTF and CSS 3

In rendering non-standard characters in the end-user's browser, there is the possibility to use a dedicated TrueType Font (TTF) which is capable to display the texts in combination with CSS 3.

In creating images for display, all the graphic files with examples characters are based on the MUFI-compliant version 3 of Andreas Stötzner's [Andron Scriptor Web](#) font. They were converted from TTF to SVG using Apache Batik and then from SVG to PNG for online display.

Additionally, the CSS 3 recommendation enables the use of web font rather than a font residing on the end-user's computer using the @font-face rule:

```
<style type="text/css">
@font-face { font-family: AndronScriptorWeb; src: url('Andron Scriptor Web.ttf'); }
.mufiFont { font-family: AndronScriptorWeb; }
</style>
```

This way it would be possible to display texts using dedicated fonts that supply the correct characters for the Unicode Private Use Area. Unfortunately the browser support for TTF web fonts currently is rather low (supported by: Mozilla Firefox 3.5+, Opera 10, Safari 3.1, Safari 4; not supported by :IE (all versions - support only Embedded Open Type), Opera 9, Google Chrome 3.0, Mozilla Firefox 2, Mozilla Firefox 3.0.) Therefore this way of usage is not recommended at present, but as more browsers support TTF web fonts, then the suggested CSS3 approach could be successfully applied.

This way it would be possible to display texts using dedicated fonts that supply the correct characters for the Unicode Private Use Area. Unfortunately the browser support for TTF web fonts currently is rather low (supported by: Mozilla Firefox 3.5+, Opera 10, Safari 3.1, Safari 4; not supported by :IE (all versions - support only Embedded Open Type), Opera 9, Google Chrome 3.0, Mozilla Firefox 2, Mozilla Firefox 3.0.) Therefore this way of usage is not recommended at present, but as more browsers support TTF web fonts, then the suggested CSS3 approach could be successfully applied.

Another possible way of using TTF would be to let the users to install dedicated font into their systems. To check whether the font is installed a javascript detection of the font's presence in the system could be implemented. This would help to decide whether use images or dedicated font during the presentation.

Note: This approach is tested and ready for implementation if the end-users decide that they require it. However, bearing all this in mind, the use of standardized mappings as described above is the preferred recommendation at the moment.

6 Conclusions and Recommendations

The comprehensive implementation of gBank into the ENRICH Manuscriptorium system greatly increases the ability to create, retrieve and display documents using old languages or unusual characters. In specific the web-service aspect of exposing any individual character's metadata through a simple and straightforward API is of great benefit to anyone working in this area. Therefore the implementation provides significant added value far beyond the project and the original scope of the workpackage.

There are a number of clear recommendations that come out of the use of Unicode and non-standard characters in the ENRICH project.

- Wherever possible projects should use a Unicode character encoding such as UTF-8.
- Projects needing to reference or record non-standard characters should in preference adopt a system such as the TEI Gaiji module recommendations for documenting their use of non-standard characters and/or the Unicode Private Use Area. ENRICH strongly recommends use of the TEI Guidelines in preference for such undertakings.
- Character normalization should be well-documented and consistently applied using standardized decomposed characters that have wide font support. Any mappings to such characters need to be clearly documented.
- All transformations, migrations, indexing and search routines should use the same table of equivalences in searching for normalized fonts.
- Although CSS3 web fonts provide a promising method to push fonts to users viewing a web page, this should not yet be recommended practice until consistently implemented across browsers.

The provision of the ENRICH gBank service far outstrips the original task for this workpackage. While the ENRICH gBank can be maintained for the life of the project, and perhaps on a best effort basis afterwards, its continual maintenance and upkeep has not been funded as part of ENRICH. No details have been provided as documentation for the API of the ENRICH gBank as a web service, partly because it is so trivial but mostly because it has not yet found a permanent home and the API will be dependent on the (straightforward) implementation of this using technologies available at its hosting location. The most significant aspect of its upkeep would be the introduction and vetting of new characters (supplied by MUFI or the ENRICH community) and the removal of characters which were late accepted into the Unicode Standard.

7 Appendices

7.1 Appendix A (a) Structural ligatures

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
efa0	æ	æ	aa	aacloelig	U+EFA0	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA CLOSED FORM
f204	æ	æ	ae	aeligred	U+F204	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH RIGHT UPPER LOOP
efae	Æ		AE	AnecklessElig	U+EFAE	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE NECKLESS A E
efa1	æ		ae	aneklesselig	U+EFA1	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE NECKLESS A E
f205	Œ		AO	AOligred	U+F205	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO NECKLESS
f206	œ		ao	aoligred	U+F206	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AO NECKLESS
efa2	ʷ		av	aneklessvlig	U+EFA2	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE NECKLESS

AV

14.1 Appendix B (b) Non-structural ligatures

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
efa3	ƒ		af	aflig	U+EFA3	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AF
efa4	Ꜧ		af	afinslig	U+EFA4	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A INSULAR F
efa5	ǻ		ag	aglig	U+EFA5	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AG
efa6	ɖ		al	allig	U+EFA6	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AL
efa7	an		an	anlig	U+EFA7	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AN
efa8	aj		aN	anscaplig	U+EFA8	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A SMALL CAPITAL N
efa9	ap		ap	aplig	U+EFA9	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AP
efaa	ar		ar	arlig	U+EFAA	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AR
efab	æ		aR	arscaplig	U+EFA B	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A SMALL CAPITAL R
efac	ƿ		ap	athornlig	U+EFA C	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A THORN
eec2	bb		bb	bblig	U+EEC2	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE BB
eec3	bj		bg	bglig	U+EEC3	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE BG
eec4	dk		ck	cklig	U+EEC4	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE CK
eec5	ct		ct	ctlig	U+EEC5	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE CT
eec6	dd		dd	drotrotlig	U+EEC6	LATIN SMALL

				6	LIGATURE D ROTUNDA D ROTUNDA
eec7	øy	ey	eylig	U+EEC 7	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE EY
eec8	fï	fa	faumllig	U+EEC 8	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE F A WITH DIAERESIS
eec9	fj	fj	fjlig	U+EEC 9	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FJ
f1bc	fö	fo	foumllig	U+F1B C	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE F O WITH DIAERESIS
eeca	fr	fr	frlig	U+EEC A	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FR
eecb	ft	ft	ftlig	U+EEC B	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FT
eecc	fü	fu	fuumllig	U+EEC C	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE F U WITH DIAERESIS
eecd	fy	fy	fylig	U+EEC D	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FY
eece	fft	fft	fftlig	U+EEC E	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FFT
eecf	ffy	ffy	ffylig	U+EEC F	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FFY
eed0	fty	fty	ftylig	U+EED 0	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE FTY
eed1	gg	gg	gglig	U+EED 1	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE GG
eed2	gđ	gd	gdlig	U+EED 2	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE GD
eed3	ğ	gd	gdrotlig	U+EED 3	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE G D ROTUNDA
eed4	ğ̃	gđ	gethlig	U+EED 4	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE G ETH

eede	Ɔ	go	golg	U+EED LATIN SMALL E LIGATURE GO
ead2	Ɔ	gp	gplig	U+EAD LATIN SMALL 2 LIGATURE GP
ead0	Ɔ	gr	grlig	U+EAD LATIN SMALL 0 LIGATURE GR
ead1	Ɔ	qv	qvinslig	U+EAD LATIN SMALL 1 LIGATURE Q INSULAR V
e8c3	ħ	hr	hrarmlig	U+E8C LATIN SMALL LETTER H LIGATED WITH ARM OF LATIN SMALL LETTER R
e8c2	Ħ	Hr	Hrarmlig	U+E8C LATIN CAPITAL LETTER H LIGATED WITH ARM OF LATIN SMALL LETTER R
e8c5	ķ	kr	krarmlig	U+E8C LATIN SMALL LETTER K LIGATED WITH ARM OF LATIN SMALL LETTER R
f4f9	ll	ll	lllig	U+F4F9 LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LL
eed5	ŋ	Ns	nscapslonglig	U+EED LATIN SMALL LIGATURE SMALL CAPITAL N LONG S
efad	œ	oc	oclig	U+EFA LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OC
eedd	Ɔ	PP	PPlig	U+EED LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE PP
eed6	Ɔ	pp	pplig	U+EED LATIN SMALL 6 LIGATURE PP
eed7	Ɔ	pp	ppflourlig	U+EED LATIN SMALL

					7	LIGATURE PP WITH FLOURISH
eba0	fä	fä	sa	slongaumllig	U+EBA0	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S A WITH DIAERESIS
f4fa	fch	fch	sch	slongchlig	U+F4FA	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S CH
eba1	fh	fh	sh	slonghlig	U+EBA1	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S H
eba2	fi	fi	si	slongilig	U+EBA2	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S I
f4fb	fj	fj	sj	slongjlig	U+F4FB	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S J
f4fc	fk	fk	sk	slongklig	U+F4FC	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S K
eba3	fl	fl	sl	slongllig	U+EBA3	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S L
eba4	fö	fö	so	slongoumllig	U+EBA4	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S O WITH DIAERESIS
eba5	fp	fp	sp	slongplig	U+EBA5	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S P
f4fd	fs		ss	slongsslig	U+F4FD	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S S
eba6	ff		ss	slongslonglig	U+EBA6	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S LONG S
eba7	ffi		ssi	slongslongilig	U+EBA7	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S LONG S I
f4fe	ffk		ssk	slongslongklig	U+F4FE	LATIN SMALL

				E	LIGATURE LONG S LONG S K
eba8	fl	ssl	slongslonglig	U+EBA 8	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S LONG S L
f4ff	ft	sst	slongslongtlig	U+F4F F	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S LONG S T
eba9	fti	sti	slongtilig	U+EBA 9	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S TI
ebaa	fr	str	slongtrlig	U+EBA A	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S TR
ebab	fu	su	slonguumlig	U+EBA B	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S U WITH DIAERESIS
ebac	ƒ	sv	slongvinslig	U+EBA C	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S INSULAR V
eada	ft	st	slongdestlig	U+EAD A	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE LONG S DESCENDING T
eed8	tr	tr	trlig	U+EED 8	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE TR
eed9	tt	tt	ttlig	U+EED 9	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE TT
eeda	ƿ	tt	trottrotlig	U+EED A	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE T ROTUNDA T ROTUNDA
eedb	ty	ty	tylig	U+EED B	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE TY
eedc	tʒ	tz	tzlig	U+EED C	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE TZ
e8c1	þ	þr	thornrarmlig	U+E8C 1	LATIN SMAL L LETTER T HORN LIGAT

ED WITH AR
M OF LATIN
SMALL LET
TER R

14.2 Appendix C Subrange 2: Small capitals

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
ef0c	ƚ		Q	qscap	U+EF0C	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL Q
ef11	ƚ		X	xscap	U+EF11	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL X
ef15	ƚ		Þ	thornscap	U+EF15	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL THORN

14.3 Appendix D Subrange 3: Enlarged minuscules

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
eee0	à	à	a	aenl	U+EEE0	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL A
eaf0	á	á	a	aenlacute	U+EAF0	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL A WITH ACUTE
efdf	ǣ	ǣ	aa	aaligenl	U+EFD F	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL LIGATURE AA
eaf1	æ	æ	ae	aeligenl	U+EAF I	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL LIGATURE AE
efde	ǽ	ǽ	ao	aoligenl	U+EFD E	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL LIGATURE AO
eaf2	ǿ	ǿ	ao	aenlosmalllig	U+EAF 2	LATIN LIGATURE ENLARGED LETTER SMALL A AND LATIN SMALL LETTER O
eee1	ɓ	ɓ	b	benl	U+EEE 1	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL B

eee2	Ċ	Ċ	c	cenl	U+EEE 2	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL C
eee3	ḍ		d	denl	U+EEE 3	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL D
eee4	ḏ		d	drotenl	U+EEE 4	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER ROTUNDA
eee5	Ḑ		ð	ethenl	U+EEE 5	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL ETH
eee6	e		e	eenl	U+EEE 6	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL E
eaf3	ɛ̣		e	eogonenl	U+EAF 3	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL WITH OGONEK
eee7	f		f	fenl	U+EEE 7	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL F
eeff	ƒ		f	finsenl	U+EEF F	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL INSULAR F
eee8	g		g	genl	U+EEE 8	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL G
eee9	h		h	henl	U+EEE 9	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL H
eeea	i		i	ienl	U+EEE A	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL I

eefd	ı	i	inodotenl	U+EEFD	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL DOTLESS I
eeeb	j	j	jenl	U+EEEB	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL J
eefe	J	j	jnodotenl	U+EEEF	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL DOTLESS J
eeec	k	k	kenl	U+EEEC	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL K
eedd	l	l	lenl	U+EEED	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL L
eeee	m	m	menl	U+EEEE	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL M
eeef	n	n	nenl	U+EEEF	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL N
eef0	o	o	oenl	U+EEF0	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL O
efdd	œ	oe	oeligenl	U+EFD	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL LIGATURE OE
eef1	p	p	penl	U+EEF1	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL P
eef2	q	q	qenl	U+EEF2	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER

eef3	r	r	renl	U+EEF 3	SMALL Q LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL R
eef4	s	s	senl	U+EEF 4	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL S
eefd	f	s	slongenl	U+EED F	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL LONG S
eef5	t	t	tenl	U+EEF 5	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL T
eef7	u	u	uenl	U+EEF 7	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL U
eef8	v	v	venl	U+EEF 8	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL V
eef9	w	w	wenl	U+EEF 9	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL W
eefa	x	x	xenl	U+EEF A	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL X
eefb	y	y	yenl	U+EEF B	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL Y
eefc	z	z	zenl	U+EEF C	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL Z
eef6	þ	þ	thornenl	U+EEF 6	LATIN ENLARGED LETTER SMALL THORN

14.4 Appendix E Subrange 4: Base-line abbreviation characters

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f1a5	9		US	USbase	U+F1A5	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN SPACING BASE-LINE CAPITAL US
f1a6	9		us	usbase	U+F1A6	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN SPACING BASE-LINE SMALL US
f142	7		ET	ET	U+F142	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN CAPITAL ET
f1a7	7		ET	ETslash	U+F1A7	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN CAPITAL ET WITH STROKE
f158	ε		et	etslash	U+F158	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN SMALL ET WITH STROKE
f159	ð		de	de	U+F159	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN SMALL DE
f1ac	;		;	sem	U+F1AC	LATIN ABBREVIATION SIGN SEMICOLON

14.5 Appendix F Subrange 5: Modified base-line abbreviation characters

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Standardized Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
ebad	fi		hs	hslonglig	U+EBA D	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE H AND LONG S
e7c7	fi		hs	hslongligbar	U+E7C 7	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE H AND LONG S WITH STROKE
ebae	k̄		ks	kslonglig	U+EBA E	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE K AND LONG S
e7c8	k̄		ks	kslongligbar	U+E7C 8	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE K AND LONG S WITH STROKE
e8b3	q̄		qr	q2app	U+E8B 3	LATIN SMALL LETTER Q LIGATED WITH ROTUNDA
e8bf	q̄		qet	q3app	U+E8B F	LATIN SMALL LETTER Q LIGATED WITH FINAL ET
e8b4	q̄		q	qcentrslstrok	U+E8B 4	LATIN SMALL LETTER Q WITH CENTRAL SLANTED STROKE
e7e4	r̄		r	rdesstrok	U+E7E 4	LATIN SMALL LETTER R WITH LONG LEG AND STROKE THROUGH DESCENDER
e8b7	ſ̄		s	slongflour	U+E8B 7	LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S WITH

Hex	Char	Char	Name	Code	Description
e8b8	ƒ	s	slongslstrok	U+E8B8	FLOURISH LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S WITH SLANTED DESCENDING STROKE
e8ba	ʋ	v	vslash	U+E8BA	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH SHORT SLASH
e8bd	ꝥ	x	xslashula	U+E8BD	LATIN SMALL LETTER X WITH SHORT SLASH ABOVE
e8be	ꝥ	x	xslashlra	U+E8BE	LATIN SMALL LETTER X WITH SHORT SLASH BELOW
e337	þ	þ	THORNbarslash	U+E337	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER THORN WITH DIAGONAL STROKE
f149	þ	þ	thornbarslash	U+F149	LATIN SMALL LETTER THORN WITH DIAGONAL STROKE
e734	ƿ	þs	thornslonglig	U+E734	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE THORN AND LONG S
e735	ƿ	þs	thornslongligbar	U+E735	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE THORN AND LONG S WITH STROKE

14.6 Appendix G Subrange 6: Combining marks

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Standardized Character	MUFI Entity Replacement	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f1c0	̣		arbar	U+F1C0	COMBINING ABBREVIATION MARK BAR ABOVE WITH DOT
f1c7	̧		erang	U+F1C7	COMBINING ABBREVIATION MARK ZIGZAG ABOVE ANGLE FORM
f1c8	̨		ercurl	U+F1C8	COMBINING ABBREVIATION MARK ZIGZAG ABOVE CURLY FORM
f1c1	̠	ra	rabar	U+F1C1	COMBINING ABBREVIATION MARK SUPERSCRIPT RA OPEN A FORM WITH BAR ABOVE
f153	̢	ur	urrot	U+F153	COMBINING ABBREVIATION MARK SUPERSCRIPT UR ROUND R FORM
f1c2	̡	ur	urlemn	U+F1C2	COMBINING ABBREVIATION MARK SUPERSCRIPT UR LEMNISKATE FORM
f1c5	̥		combcurlhigh	U+F1C5	COMBINING CURL HIGH POSITION
f1ca	̦		combdothigh	U+F1CA	COMBINING DOT ABOVE HIGH POSITION

f1cc ̂

combcurlbar U+F1C COMBINING
C CURLY BAR
ABOVE

f1fc ̃

combtripbrevebl U+F1F COMBINING
C TRIPLE BREVE
BELOW

14.7 Appendix H Subrange 7: Combining superscript characters

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f036	◌ ^{an}	◌ ^a	an	anligsup	U+F036	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AN
f03a	◌ ^{aN}	◌ ^a	aN	anscapligsup	U+F03A	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A SMALL CAPITAL N
f038	◌ ^{ar}	◌ ^a	ar	arligsup	U+F038	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AR
f130	◌ ^{aR}	◌ ^a	aR	arscapligsup	U+F130	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LIGATURE A SMALL CAPITAL R
f012	◌ ^b	◌ ^b	b	bsup	U+F012	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER B
f013	◌ ^B	◌ ^b	B	bscapsup	U+F013	COMBINING LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL B
f016	◌ ^D	◌ ^d	D	dscapsup	U+F016	COMBINING LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL D
f135	◌ ^e	◌ ^e	e	eogonsup	U+F135	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER WITH

f136	ē	ē	e	emacrsup	U+F136	OGONEK COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH MACRON
f017	ƒ	ƒ	f	fsup	U+F017	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER F
f02f	ï	ı	i	inodotsup	U+F02F	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER DOTLESS I
f030	ĵ	ĵ	j	jsup	U+F030	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER J
f031	ĵ	ĵ	j	jnodotsup	U+F031	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER DOTLESS J
f01c	Ɔ		k	kscapsup	U+F01C	COMBINING LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL K
f13e	ō		o	oogonsup	U+F13E	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH OGONEK
f032	ø		o	oslashsup	U+F032	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE
f13f	ō		o	omacrsup	U+F13F	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH

f03e	ø	or	orrotssup	U+F03E	MACRON COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O R ROTUNDA
f03f	ø	orum	orumsup	U+F03F	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O RUM
f025	þ	p	psup	U+F025	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER P
f033	q̇	q	qsup	U+F033	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER Q
f040	ꝛ	rum	rumsup	U+F040	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER RUM
f02a	ṭ	T	tscapsup	U+F02A	COMBINING LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL T
f03b	ṭ	T	trotsup	U+F03B	COMBINING LATIN LETTER T ROTUNDA
f03c	ẇ	w	wsup	U+F03C	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER W
f02b	ÿ	y	ysup	U+F02B	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER Y
f03d	þ	þ	thornsup	U+F03D	COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER THORN

14.8 Appendix I Subrange 8: Punctuation marks

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Standardized Character	Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f1f8	·	·		hidot	U+F1F8	DISTINCTIO
f1e2	,	,		posit	U+F1E2	COMMA POSITURA
f1e3	ʹ	,		ductsimpl	U+F1E3	HIGH COMMA POSITURA (SIMPLEX DUCTUS)
f1ea	;	;		punctvers	U+F1E	PUNCTUS VERSUS A
f1e4	⸗	⸗		punctposit	U+F1E4	PUNCTUS WITH COMMA POSITURA
f1e5	⸘	⸘		colmidcomposit	U+F1E5	COLON WITH MIDDLE COMMA POSITURA
f1f2	⸚	⸚		bidotscomposit	U+F1F2	TWO DOTS OVER COMMA POSITURA
f1e6	⸛	⸛		tridotscomposit	U+F1E6	THREE DOTS WITH COMMA POSITURA
f161	⸜	⸜		punctelev	U+F161	PUNCTUS ELEVATUS
f1f0	⸝	⸝		punctelevdiag	U+F1F0	PUNCTUS ELEVATUS DIAGONAL STROKE
f1fa	⸞	⸞		punctelevhiback	U+F1F A	PUNCTUS ELEVATUS WITH HIGH BACK
f1fb	⸟	⸟		punctelevhack	U+F1F B	PUNCTUS ELEVATUS WITH HACKLE
f1f5	⸠	⸠		punctflex	U+F1F5	PUNCTUS FLEXUS
f1e7	!	!		punctexclam	U+F1E7	PUNCTUS EXCLAMATIVUS
f160	⸡	⸡		punctinter	U+F160	PUNCTUS INTERROGATIVUS
f1e8	⸢	·		punctintertilde	U+F1E8	PUNCTUS INTERROGATIVUS HORIZONTAL TILDE
f1f1	⸣	·		punctinterlemn	U+F1F1	PUNCTUS

					INTERROGATIVUS LEMNISKATE FORM
f1f9	~	~	wavylin	U+F1F9	WAVY LINE
f1e0	?	,	medcom	U+F1E0	MEDIEVAL COMMA
f1e1	¶	¶	parag	U+F1E1	PARAGRAPHUS
f1ec	∴		renvoi	U+F1E	SIGNE DE RENVOI C
f1f4	/	/	virgsusp	U+F1F4	VIRGULA SUSPENSIVA
f1f7	/	/	virgmin	U+F1F7	SHORT VIRGULA

14.9 Appendix J Subrange 9: Critical and epigraphical signs

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f1da	◦			midring	U+F1DA	MIDDLE RING

14.10 Appendix K Subrange 10: Metrical symbols

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f70b	ǎ	'		metrancacute	U+F70B	METRICAL SYMBOL ANCEPS WITH ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS)
f719	ǻ	"		metrancdblac	U+F719	METRICAL SYMBOL ANCEPS WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS AND ALLITERATION)
f70c	ǰ	'		metrancgrave	U+F70C	METRICAL SYMBOL ANCEPS WITH GRAVE (PRIMARY STRESS)
f71a	ǻ	"		metrancdblgrave	U+F71A	METRICAL SYMBOL ANCEPS WITH DOUBLE GRAVE (SECONDARY STRESS AND ALLITERATION)
f706	ǿ	'		metrbreveacute	U+F706	METRICAL SYMBOL BREVE WITH ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS)
f717	ǿ	"		metrbrevedblac	U+F717	METRICAL SYMBOL BREVE WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS AND ALLITERATION)
f707	ǿ	'		metrbrevegrave	U+F707	METRICAL SYMBOL BREVE WITH GRAVE

f718	◌̂	"	metrbrevedblgrave	U+F718	(SECONDARY STRESS) METRICAL SYMBOL BREVE WITH DOUBLE GRAVE (SECONDARY STRESS AND ALLITERATION)
f704	◌́	'	metrmacracute	U+F704	METRICAL SYMBOL LONGUM WITH ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS)
f715	◌̂̂	"	metrmacrdblac	U+F715	METRICAL SYMBOL LONGUM WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (SECONDARY STRESS)
f705	◌̀	'	metrmacrgrave	U+F705	METRICAL SYMBOL LONGUM WITH GRAVE (SECONDARY STRESS)
f716	◌̂̂	"	metrmacrdblgrave	U+F716	METRICAL SYMBOL LONGUM WITH DOUBLE GRAVE (SECONDARY STRESS AND ALLITERATION)
f708	◌̂́	'	metrmacrbreveacute	U+F708	METRICAL SYMBOL BREVE ABOVE LONGUM WITH ACUTE (SHORT OR LONG SYLLABLE WITH PRIMARY STRESS)
f709	◌̀́	'	metrmacrbrevegrave	U+F709	METRICAL SYMBOL BREVE ABOVE LONGUM WITH GRAVE (SHORT

					OR LONG SYLLABLE WITH SECONDARY STRESS)
f71b	ꞥ	ꞥ	'	metrdblbreveamacracute U+F71B	METRICAL SYMBOL RESOLVED LIFT WITH ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS)
f71c	ꞥ	ꞥ	"	metrdblbreveacrdblac U+F71C	METRICAL SYMBOL RESOLVED LIFT WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (PRIMARY STRESS AND ALLITERATION)

14.11 Appendix L Subrange 11: Additional number forms

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f1bd	o		0	smallzero	U+F1BD	SMALL BASE LINE ZERO SIGN
f1be	v		V	Vmod	U+F1BE	MODIFIER CAPITAL LETTER V
f1bf	x		X	Xmod	U+F1BF	MODIFIER CAPITAL LETTER X

14.12 Appendix M Subrange 12: Weight, currency and measurement

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f2e0	⅃			romaslibr	U+F2E0	ROMAN LIBRALIS SIGN AS
f2e2	⅄	x	x	romscapxbar	U+F2E2	LATIN SMALL CAPITAL LETTER X WITH BAR (DENARIUS SIGN)
f2e3	ⅅ	y	y	romscapybar	U+F2E3	LATIN SMALL CAPITAL LETTER Y WITH BAR
f2e4	ⅆ	D	D	romscapdslash	U+F2E4	LATIN SMALL CAPITAL LETTER D WITH SLASH
f2e6	ⅇ	3	3	dram	U+F2E6	PHARMACEUTICAL DRAM SIGN
f2e7	ⅈ	v	v	ecu	U+F2E7	ECU SIGN
f2e8	ⅉ	fl	fl	florloop	U+F2E8	FLOREN SIGN WITH LOOP
f2e9	⅊	g	g	grosch	U+F2E9	GROSCHEN SIGN
f2ea	⅋	£	£	libradut	U+F2E A	DUTCH LIBRA SIGN
f2eb	⅌	£	£	librafren	U+F2E B	FRENCH LIBRA SIGN
f2ec	⅍	£	£	libraital	U+F2E C	ITALIAN LIBRA SIGN
f2ed	ⅎ	£	£	libraflem	U+F2E D	FLEMISH LIBRA SIGN
f2ee	⅏	£	£	liranuov	U+F2E E	LIRA NUOVA SIGN
f2ef	⅐	£	£	lirasterl	U+F2E F	LIRA STERLINA SIGN
f2f0	⅑			markold	U+F2F0	OLD MARK SIGN
f2f1	⅒			markflour	U+F2F1	OLD FLOURISH MARK SIGN
f2f2	⅓	m	m	msign	U+F2F2	MARKED SMALL LETTER M SIGN
f2f3	⅔	m	m	msignflour	U+F2F3	FLOURISHED SMALL LETTER M SIGN

f2f4	€		obol	U+F2F4 PHARMACEUTICAL OBOLUS SIGN
f2f5	ⷈ̄r		penningar	U+F2F5 PENNING SIGN
f2f6	ꝛ		reichtalold	U+F2F6 OLD REICHSTALER SIGN
f2f7	ſ		schillgerm	U+F2F7 GERMAN SCHILLING SIGN
f2f8	ſℓ		schillgermscript	U+F2F8 GERMAN SCRIPT SCHILLING SIGN
f2f9	ꝛ		scudi	U+F2F9 SCUDI SIGN
f2fd	ⷈ̄	oz	ouncescript	U+F2F SCRIPT OUNCE D SIGN

14.13 Appendix N Subrange 13: Modified base-line characters

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e7b2	ñ		n	nbar	U+E7B2	LATIN SMALL LETTER N WITH BAR
e74e	v̄		v	vbar	U+E74E	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH BAR
e77b	ÿ		y	ybar	U+E77B	LATIN SMALL LETTER Y WITH BAR

14.14 Appendix O Subrange 15: Characters with macron or overline

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Standardized Character	MUFI Entity Replacement	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f00a	̄	̄	macrhigh	U+F00A	COMBINING HIGH MACRON WITH FIXED HEIGHT (PART-WIDTH)
f00b	̄	̄	macrmed	U+F00B	COMBINING MEDIUM-HIGH MACRON WITH FIXED HEIGHT (PART-WIDTH)
f00c	̄	̄	ovlhigh	U+F00C	COMBINING HIGH OVERLINE WITH FIXED HEIGHT (FULL-WIDTH)
f00d	̄	̄	ovlmed	U+F00D	COMBINING MEDIUM-HIGH OVERLINE WITH FIXED HEIGHT (FULL-WIDTH)
e44d	ḃ	ḃ	bovlmed	U+E44D	LATIN SMALL LETTER B WITH MEDIUM-HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)
f7b5	̄	C	Covlhigh = C + bar	U+F7B5 (U+F7B5 = 0043 + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (

f23f	Ɔ	C	romnumCrevovl U+F23F = CONbase + (U+F23F bar = 2183+ 0305)	= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C + COMBINING OVERLINE) ROMAN NUMERAL REVERSED ONE HUNDRED WITH OVERLINE (= ROMAN NUMERAL REVERSED ONE HUNDRED+ COMBINING OVERLINE)
f7b6	Ɔ̄	D	Dovlhigh = D + U+F7B6 bar (U+F7B6 = 0044 + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER D WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER D + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e491	đ	D	dovlmed U+E491	LATIN SMALL LETTER D WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)
e0bc	Ē	E	Eogonmacr = U+E0BC Eogon + (U+E0B combmacr C = 0118+ 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND MACRON (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E

e4bc	ē	e	eogonmacr eogon comblmacr	= U+E4BC + (U+E4B C = 0119+ 0304)	WITH OGONEK+ COMBINING MACRON) LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK+ COMBINING MACRON)
e517	ĥ	h	hovlmed	U+E517	LATIN SMALL LETTER H WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)
e150	Ī	I	Iovlhigh bar	= I + U+E150 (U+E150 = 0049 + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e550	ī	i	iovlmed bar	= i + U+E550 (U+E550 = 0069 + 0305)	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH + COMBINING

e154	̄	̄	J	Jmacrhigh = J + U+E154 combmacr (U+E154 = 004A + 0304)	OVERLINE) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J WITH HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING MACRON)
e152	̄	̄	J	Jovlhigh = J + U+E152 bar (U+E152 = 004A + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e554	̄		j	jmacrmed = j + U+E554 combmacr (U+E554 = 006A + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH MEDIUM-HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER J + COMBINING MACRON)
e552	̄		j	jovlmed = j + U+E552 bar (U+E552 = 006A + 0305)	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH MEDIUM-HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL

e7c3	ķ	k	kovlmed	U+E7C3	LETTER J + COMBINING OVERLINE) LATIN SMALL LETTER K WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)
e5b1	l̄	l	lovlmed	U+E5B1	LATIN SMALL LETTER L WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)
f7b4	Ļ	L	Lovlhigh = L + bar	U+F7B4 (U+F7B4 = 004C + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER L WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER L + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e596	l̄	l	lmacrhigh = l + combmacr	U+E596 (U+E596 = 006C + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER L WITH HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER L + COMBINING MACRON)
e58c	l̄	l	lovlhigh = l + bar	U+E58C (U+E58 C = 006C + 0305)	LATIN SMALL LETTER L WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER L + COMBINING MACRON)

				=	LATIN SMALL LETTER L + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e1b8	Ṁ	M	Mmacrhigh M + combmacr	= U+E1B8 (U+E1B8 = 004D + 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER M WITH HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER M + COMBINING MACRON)
e1d2	Ṃ	M	Movlhigh + bar	= M U+E1D2 (U+E1D 2 = 004D + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER M WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER M + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e5b8	ṁ	m	mmacrmed + combmacr	= m U+E5B8 (U+E5B8 = 006D + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER M WITH MEDIUM- HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER M + COMBINING MACRON)
e5d2	ṃ	m	movlmed bar	= m + U+E5D2 (U+E5D 2 = 006D + 0305)	LATIN SMALL LETTER M WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE

				(ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER M + COMBINING OVERLINE)
e1dc	Ñ	N	Nmacrhigh = N U+E1D + combmacr C (U+E1D C = 004E + 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER N WITH HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER N + COMBINING MACRON)
e5dc	ñ	n	nmacrmed = n U+E5D + combmacr C (U+E5D C = 006E + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER N WITH MEDIUM-HIGH MACRON (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER N + COMBINING MACRON)
e252	Ø	O	Oslashmacr = U+E252 + (U+E252 combmacr = 00D8 + 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND MACRON (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING MACRON)
e652	ø	o	oslashmacr = U+E652 + (U+E652 combmacr = 00F8 + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND MACRON (= LATIN

					SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING MACRON)
e25d	Œ	OE	OEligmacr OElig comblmacr	= U+E25D + (U+E25 D 0152+ 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OE WITH MACRON (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OE+ COMBINING MACRON)
e65d	œ	oe	oeligmacr oelig comblmacr	= U+E65D + (U+E65 D 0153+ 0304)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE WITH MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE+ COMBINING MACRON)
e7cc	ō	o	oopenmacr	U+E7CC	LATIN SMALL LETTER OPEN O WITH MACRON
e665	ṑ	p	pmacr = p comblmacr	+ U+E665 (U+E665 = 0070 + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER P WITH MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER P + COMBINING MACRON)
e681	ṙ	q	qmacr = q comblmacr	+ U+E681 (U+E681 = 0071 + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Q WITH MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Q + COMBINING MACRON)
e79e	ſ	s	slongovlmed	U+E79E	LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S WITH

					MEDIUM-HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)
e34d	Ṽ	V	Vmacr = V + U+E34D combmacr (U+E34D = 0056 + 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V WITH MACRON (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING MACRON)	
f7b2	Ṛ	V	Vovlhigh = V + U+F7B2 bar (U+F7B2 = 0056 + 0305)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING OVERLINE)	
e74d	ṽ	v	vmacr = v + U+E74D combmacr (U+E74D = 0076 + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING MACRON)	
e357	Ŵ	W	Wmacr = W + U+E357 combmacr (U+E357 = 0057 + 0304)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER W WITH MACRON (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER W + COMBINING MACRON)	
e757	ŵ	w	wmacr = w + U+E757 combmacr (U+E757 = 0077 + 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER W WITH MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING MACRON)	

				0304)	MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING MACRON)
f7b3	̄	X	Xovlhigh = X + U+F7B3 bar		LATIN CAPITAL LETTER X WITH HIGH OVERLINE (ABOVE CHARACTER) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER X)
e7a2	þ	þ	thornovlmed	U+E7A2	LATIN SMALL LETTER THORN WITH MEDIUM- HIGH OVERLINE (ACROSS ASCENDER)

14.15 Appendix P Subrange 16: Characters with acute accent

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
efe0	Á		AA	AAligacute AAlig combacute	= U+EFE0 + (U+EFE0 = EF90 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe1	á		aa	aaligacute aalig combacute	= U+EFE1 + (U+EFE1 = EF91 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe2	Ã		AO	AOligacute AOlig combacute	= U+EFE2 + (U+EFE2 = EF92 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe3	ã		ao	aoligacute aolig combacute	= U+EFE3 + (U+EFE3 = EF93 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AO WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AO + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe4	Ã		AU	AUligacute AUlig combacute	= U+EFE4 + (U+EFE4 = EF94	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AU

				+ 0301)	WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AU + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe5	á	au	auligacute aulig combacute	= U+EFE5 + (U+EFE5 = EF95 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AU WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AU + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe6	Á	av	AVligacute AVlig combacute	= U+EFE6 + (U+EFE6 = EF96 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe7	á	av	avligacute avlig combacute	= U+EFE7 + (U+EFE7 = EF97 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
ebb0	Ǻ	AV	AVligslashacute = AVligslash combacute	U+EBB0 + (U+EBB0 = EF98+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV WITH STROKE AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV WITH STROKE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)

ebb1	á		av	avligslashacute = avligslash combacutecute	U+EBB1 + (U+EBB1 1 EF99+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV WITH STROKE AND ACUTE (LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV WITH STROKE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e044	Ĕ	ĕ	B	Bacutecute = B combacutecute	+ U+E044 (U+E044 = 0042 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER B WITH ACUTE (LATIN CAPITAL LETTER B + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e444	ĕ	ě	b	bacutecute = b combacutecute	+ U+E444 (U+E444 = 0062 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER B WITH ACUTE (LATIN SMALL LETTER B + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e077	Ď	ď	D	Dacutecute = D combacutecute	+ U+E077 (U+E077 = 0044 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER D WITH ACUTE (LATIN CAPITAL LETTER D + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e477	ď	đ	d	dacutecute = d combacutecute	+ U+E477 (U+E477 = 0064 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER D WITH ACUTE (LATIN SMALL LETTER D + COMBINING

					0301)	=	LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR F + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e116	Ĥ	ĥ	H	Hacute = H + U+E116 combacute (U+E116	= 0048 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER H WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER H + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	
e516	ĥ		h	hacute = h + U+E516 combacute (U+E516	= 0068 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER H WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER H + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	
e153	Ĵ		J	Jacute = J + U+E153 combacute (U+E153	= 004A + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	
e553	ĵ		j	jacute = j + U+E553 combacute (U+E553	= 006A + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER J + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	
ebb5	Ŭ		M	Muncacute = U+EBB5 Munc + (U+EBB combacute 5 =	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER		

				F11A+ 0301)	UNCIAL M WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER UNCIAL M+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
ebb6	ṁ	M	muncacute munc combacut	= U+EBB6 + (U+EBB 6 F225+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER UNCIAL M COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e259	Œ	OE	OEligacute OElig combacut	= U+E259 + (U+E259 = 0152 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OE WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OE + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e659	œ	oe	oeligacute oelig combacut	= U+E659 + (U+E659 = 0153 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
efe8	Œ	OO	OOLigacute OOLig combacut	= U+EFE8 + (U+EFE 8 = F20A + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OO WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OO + COMBINING ACUTE

					ACCENT)
e9e9	ó	oo	ooligacute oolig combacute	= U+E9E9 + (U+E9E 9 = F20B + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OO WITH ACUTE (LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OO + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e9b9	í	r	rrotacute + combacute	= rrot U+E9B9 (U+E9B 9 = F20E + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER R ROTUNDA WITH ACUTE (LATIN SMALL LETTER R ROTUNDA + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e9af	Ń	s	slongacute slong combacute	= U+E9AF + (U+E9A F = 017F + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e2e2	Ť	T	Tacute combacute	= T + U+E2E2 (U+E2E2 = 0054 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER T WITH ACUTE (LATIN CAPITAL LETTER T + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e6e2	ť	t	tacute combacute	= t + U+E6E2 (U+E6E2 = 0074 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER T WITH ACUTE (LATIN SMALL LETTER T + COMBINING

e33a	Ŵ	V	Vacute = V combacute	+ U+E33A (U+E33A = 0056 + 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e73a	ŵ	v	vacute = v combacute	+ U+E73A (U+E73A = 0076 + 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
ebba	þ	V	Vinsacute Vins combacute	= U+EBB + A (U+EBB A = F210+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) WITH ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND)+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
ebbb	þ	v	vinsacute = vins + combacute	U+EBBB (U+EBB B = F211+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) WITH ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND)+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e737	þ	þ	thornacute	= U+E737	LATIN SMALL

thorn + (U+E737 LETTER
combacute = 00FE THORN WITH
+ 0301) ACUTE (=
LATIN SMALL
LETTER
THORN +
COMBINING
ACUTE
ACCENT)

14.16 Appendix Q Subrange 17: Characters with double acute accent

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e025	Á	Á	A	Adblac = A + combdblac	U+E025 (U+E025 = 0041 + 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A WITH DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e425	á	á	a	adblac = a + combdblac	U+E425 (U+E425 = 0061 + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
efea	Ā	Ā	AA	AAligdblac = AAlig + combdblac	U+EFEA (U+EFEA = EF90 + 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA WITH DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
efeb	ā	ā	aa	aaligdblac = aalig + combdblac	U+EFEB (U+EFEB = EF91 + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA WITH DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)

e041	Æ	AE	AEligdblac = AElig comdblac	U+E041 + (U+E041 = 00C6 + 030B)	DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e441	æ	ae	aeligdblac aelig comdblac	= U+E441 + (U+E441 = 00E6 + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc0	Ǽ	AO	AOligdblac = AOlig comdblac	U+EBC0 + (U+EBC 0 = EF92 + 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc1	ǽ	ao	aoligdblac aolig comdblac	= U+EBC1 + (U+EBC 1 = EF93 + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AO WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AO + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc2	Ǽ	AV	AVligdblac	U+EBC2	LATIN

			= AVlig + (U+EBC CAPITAL comdblac 2 = EF96 LIGATURE AV + 030B) WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc3	á	av	avligdblac = U+EBC3 LATIN SMALL avlig + (U+EBC LIGATURE AV comdblac 3 = EF97 WITH DOUBLE + 030B) ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e0d1	É	E	Edblac = E U+E0D1 LATIN + comdblac (U+E0D CAPITAL 1 = 0045 LETTER E + 030B) WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e4d1	é	e	edblac = e + U+E4D1 LATIN SMALL comdblac (U+E4D LETTER E 1 = 0065 WITH DOUBLE + 030B) ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e143	Ī	I	Idblac = I + U+E143 LATIN comdblac (U+E143 CAPITAL = 0049 + LETTER I WITH 030B) DOUBLE ACUTE (=

				LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e543	í	i	idblac = i + U+E543 combdblac (U+E543 = 0069 + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e162	Ĵ	J	Jdblac = J + U+E162 combdblac (U+E162 = 004A + 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e562	ĵ	j	jdblac = j + U+E562 combdblac (U+E562 = 006A + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER J + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc6	Œ	O	Oslashdblac = Oslash + U+EBC6 combdblac 6 = 00D8+ 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O

					WITH STROKE+ COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc7	ø	o	oslashdblac = oslash + combdblac	U+EBC7 (U+EBC 7 = 00F8+ 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE+ COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc8	Œ	OE	OEligdblac = OElig + combdblac	U+EBC8 (U+EBC 8 = 0152 + 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OE WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OE + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc9	œ	oe	oeligdblac = oelig + combdblac	U+EBC9 (U+EBC 9 = 0153 + 030B)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
efec	Œ	OO	OOLigdblac = OOLig + combdblac	U+EFEC (U+EFE C = F20A 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OO WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL

				LIGATURE OO + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
efed	ó	oo	ooligdblac = U+EFE oolig + D comdblac (U+EFE D = ACUTE (= F20B + LATIN SMALL 030B)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OO WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OO + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e34b	Ť	V	Vdblac = V U+E34B + comdblac (U+E34B = 0056 + LETTER V 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e74b	ř	v	vdblac = v + U+E74B comdblac (U+E74B = 0076 + WITH DOUBLE 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e350	Ŧ	W	Wdblac = U+E350 W + (U+E350 comdblac = 0057 + LETTER W 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER W + WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER W + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE

				ACCENT)
e750	ŵ	w	wdblac = w U+E750 + combdblac (U+E750	LATIN SMALL LETTER W WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e37c	Ỳ	Y	Ydblac = Y U+E37C + combdblac (U+E37C	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e77c	ÿ	y	ydblac = y + U+E77C comdblac (U+E77C	LATIN SMALL LETTER Y WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Y + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebca	Ỳ	YY	YYligdblac U+EBC = YYlig + A comdblac (U+EBC	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE YY WITH DOUBLE ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE YY + COMBINING DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebcb	ÿ	yy	yyligdblac = U+EBCB yylig + (U+EBC comdblac B = F213	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE YY WITH DOUBLE

+ 030B) ACUTE (=
LATIN SMALL
LIGATURE YY
+ COMBINING
DOUBLE
ACUTE
ACCENT)

14.17 Appendix R Subrange 18: Characters with dot above

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
efee	Ä		AA	AAligdot AAlig combdot	= U+EFE + E (U+EFE E EF90 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
efef	ä		aa	aaligdot = + combdot	= aalig U+EFEF (U+EFEF F EF91 0307)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e043	Æ		AE	AEligdot AElig combdot	= U+E043 + (U+E043 = 00C6 + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e443	æ		ae	aeligdot = + combdot	= aelig U+E443 (U+E443 = 00E6 + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
eff0	Ȧ		AY	AYligdot AYlig combdot	= U+EFF0 + (U+EFF 0 EF9A 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AY WITH DOT ABOVE (=

					LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AY + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
eff1	ÿ	ay	ayligdot = aylig + combdot	U+EFF1 (U+EFF1 1 = EF9B + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AY WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AY + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd0	İ	B	bscapdot = bscap + combdot	U+EBD0 (U+EBD0 0 = 0299 + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL B WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL B + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd1	Đ	d	drotddot = drot + combdot	U+EBD1 (U+EBD1 1 = F109 + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER D ROTUNDA WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER D ROTUNDA + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd2	Đ	D	dscapdot = dscap + combdot	U+EBD2 (U+EBD2 2 = 1D05 + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL D WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL D + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd3	ƒ	F	Finsdot = Fins + combdot	U+EBD3 (U+EBD3 3 = F10C + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER F INSULAR WITH DOT ABOVE

				0307)	ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR F + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd4	ḟ	f	finsdot = fins + U+EBD combdot 4		LATIN SMALL LETTER (U+EBD INSULAR F 4 = WITH DOT F10D + ABOVE (= 0307) LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR F + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd5	ḡ	f	finssemiclosedot U+EBD = finssemiclose 5 + combdot (U+EBD 5 =		LATIN SMALL LETTER SEMI- CLOSED INSULAR F WITH DOT ABOVE (= 0307) LATIN SMALL LETTER SEMI- CLOSED INSULAR F+ COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd6	Ḣ	f	finsclosedot = U+EBD finsclose + 6 combdot (U+EBD 6 =		LATIN SMALL LETTER CLOSED INSULAR F WITH DOT ABOVE (= 0307) LATIN SMALL LETTER CLOSED INSULAR F+ COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebd7	Ḥ	F	fscapdot = fscap U+EBD + combdot 7		LATIN LETTER SMALL (U+EBD CAPITAL F 7 = EF05 WITH DOT + 0307) ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL

ef20	ġ	G	gscapdot gscap combdot	= U+EF20 + (U+EF20 = 0262 + 0307)	CAPITAL F + COMBINING DOT ABOVE) LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL G WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL G + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebda	ĥ	H	hscapdot hscap combdot	= U+EBD + A (U+EBD A = 029C + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL H WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL H + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e15c	ĵ	J	Jdot = combdot	J + U+E15C (U+E15 C = 004A + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e168	Ķ	K	Kdot = combdot	K + U+E168 (U+E168 = 004B + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER K WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER K + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e568	ķ	k	kdot = combdot	k + U+E568 (U+E568 = 006B + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER K WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL

					LETTER K + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebdb	ķ	k	kscapdot kscap combdot	= U+EBD + B (U+EBD B = 1D0B + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL K WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL K + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e19e	Ĺ	L	Ldot = L combdot	+ U+E19E (U+E19 E = 004C + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER L WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER L + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e59e	ĺ	l	ldot = l combdot	+ U+E59E (U+E59 E = 006C + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER L WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER L + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebdc	Ľ	L	lscapdot = lscap + combdot	U+EBD C (U+EBD C = 029F + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL L WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL L + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebdd	ṁ	M	mscapdot mscap combdot	= U+EBD + D (U+EBD D = 1D0D + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL M WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL

					CAPITAL M + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ef21	ñ	N	nscapdot nscap combdot	= U+EF21 + (U+EF21 = 0274 + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL N WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL N + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebcd	ø	O	Oslashdot Oslash combdot	= U+EBC + D (U+EBC D = 00D8 + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebce	ø	o	oslashdot oslash combdot	= U+EBC + E (U+EBC E = 00F8 + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ebcf	þ	P	pscapdot pscap combdot	= U+EBC + F (U+EBC F = 1D18 + 0307)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL P WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL P + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e282	Œ	Œ	Qdot combdot	= Q + U+E282 (U+E282 = 0051 +	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Q

					0307)	WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Q + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e682	q̇	q̇	q	qdot = q + U+E682 combdot (U+E682 = 0071 + 0307)		LATIN SMALL LETTER Q WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Q + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ef22	Ŕ	Ŕ	R	rscapdot = rscap + combdot U+EF22 (U+EF22 = 0280 + 0307)		LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL R WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL R + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ef23	Ŗ	Ŗ	S	sscapdot = sscap + combdot U+EF23 (U+EF23 = EF0E + 0307)		LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL S WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL S + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
ef24	Ť	Ť	T	tscapdot = tscap + combdot U+EF24 (U+EF24 = 1D1B + 0307)		LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL T WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL T + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e315	Ů	Ů	U	Udot = U + U+E315 combdot (U+E315 = 0055 +		LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U

					0307)	WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)
e715	ù	u	udot = u combdot	+ U+E715 (U+E715 = 0075 + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER U WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)	
e34c	Ÿ	V	Vdot = V combdot	+ U+E34C (U+E34 C = 0056 + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)	
e74c	ÿ	v	vdot = v combdot	+ U+E74C (U+E74 C = 0076 + 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)	
e3e7	ÿ̇	V	Vinsdot = Vins + combdot	U+E3E7 (U+E3E 7 = F210 + 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) WITH DOT ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) + COMBINING DOT ABOVE)	
e7e7	ÿ̈	v	vinsdot = vins combdot	+ U+E7E7 (U+E7E LETTER	LATIN SMALL LETTER	

7 = F211 INSULAR V
+ 0307) (VEND) WITH
DOT ABOVE (=
LATIN SMALL
LETTER
INSULAR V
(VEND) +
COMBINING
DOT ABOVE)

14.18 Appendix S Subrange 19: Characters with dot below

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
eff2	ⱶ		AA	AAligdotbl AAlig combdotbl	= U+EFF2 + (U+EFF2 2 EF90 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff3	ⱷ		aa	aaligdotbl aalig combdotbl	= U+EFF3 + (U+EFF3 3 EF91 0323)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e036	Æ		AE	AEligdotbl AElig combdotbl	= U+E036 + (U+E036 = 00C6 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e436	æ		ae	aeligdotbl aelig combdotbl	= U+E436 + (U+E436 = 00E6 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff4	ⱸ		AO	AOligdotbl AOlig combdotbl	= U+EFF4 + (U+EFF4 4 EF92 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO WITH DOT BELOW (=

					LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AO + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff5	ə	ao	aoligdotbl aolig combdotbl	= U+EFF5 + (U+EFF 5 = EF93 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AO + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff6	Ā	AU	AUligdotbl AUlig combdotbl	= U+EFF6 + (U+EFF 6 = EF94 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AU + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff7	ą	au	auligdotbl aulig combdotbl	= U+EFF7 + (U+EFF 7 = EF95 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AU + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff8	Ā	AV	AVligdotbl AVlig combdotbl	= U+EFF8 + (U+EFF 8 = EF96 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
eff9	ą	av	avligdotbl avlig combdotbl	= U+EFF9 + (U+EFF 9 = EF97 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING

					DOT BELOW)
effa	Ȧ	AY	AYligdotbl AYlig combdotbl	= U+EFF + A (U+EFF A EF9A 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AY = WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AY + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
effb	ȧ	ay	ayligdotbl aylig combdotbl	= U+EFF + B (U+EFF B EF9B 0323)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AY WITH DOT = BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AY + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef25	Ȣ	B	bscapdotbl bscap combdotbl	= U+EF25 + (U+EF2 5 = 0299 + 0323)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL B WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL B + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e066	Ç	C	Cdotbl = C combdotbl	+ U+E066 (U+E066 = 0043 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e466	ç	c	cdotbl = c combdotbl	+ U+E466 (U+E466 = 0063 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER C WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER C + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef26	ȡ	D	dscapdotbl	= U+EF26	LATIN LETTER

			dscap combdotbl	+ (U+EF2 6 1D05 0323)	SMALL = CAPITAL + WITH BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL D + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e08f	Ð	Ð	ETHdotbl ETH combdotbl	= U+E08F + (U+E08 F 00D0 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL = LETTER ETH + WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER ETH + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e48f	ð	ð	ethdotbl + combdotbl	= eth U+E48F (U+E48 F = 00F0 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER ETH WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER ETH + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e0ee	Ɖ	Ɖ	Fdotbl combdotbl	= F + U+E0E E (U+E0E E = 0046 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER F WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER F + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e4ee	ƒ	f	fdotbl combdotbl	= f + U+E4E E (U+E4E E = 0066 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER F WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER F + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e3e5	Ɔ	Ɔ	Finsdotbl Fins combdotbl	= U+E3E5 + (U+E3E 5	LATIN CAPITAL = LETTER

				F10C + INSULAR F 0323) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR F + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e7e5	ƒ	f	finsdotbl = U+E7E5 LATIN SMALL fins + (U+E7E LETTER combdotbl 5 = INSULAR F F10D + WITH DOT 0323) BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR F + COMBINING DOT BELOW)	
e101	Ɔ	G	Gdotbl = G + U+E101 LATIN combdotbl (U+E101 CAPITAL = 0047 + LETTER G 0323) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER G + COMBINING DOT BELOW)	
e501	g	G	gdotbl = g + U+E501 LATIN SMALL combdotbl (U+E501 LETTER G = 0067 + WITH DOT 0323) BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER G + COMBINING DOT BELOW)	
ef27	ḡ	G	gscapdotbl = U+EF27 LATIN LETTER gscap + (U+EF2 SMALL combdotbl 7 = 0262 CAPITAL G + 0323) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL G + COMBINING DOT BELOW)	
e151	J	J	Jdotbl = J + U+E151 LATIN	

			combdotbl	(U+E151 CAPITAL = 004A LETTER J + 0323) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e551	j̇	j	jdotbl = j combdotbl	+ U+E551 LATIN SMALL (U+E551 LETTER J = 006A WITH DOT + 0323) BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER J + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef28	Ł	L	lscapdotbl lscap combdotbl	= U+EF28 LATIN LETTER + (U+EF2 SMALL 8 = 029F CAPITAL L + 0323) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL L + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef29	Ṁ	M	mscapdotbl mscap combdotbl	= U+EF29 LATIN LETTER + (U+EF2 SMALL 9 = CAPITAL M 1D0D + WITH DOT 0323) BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL M + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef2a	Ṇ	N	nscapdotbl nscap combdotbl	= U+EF2 LATIN LETTER + A SMALL (U+EF2 CAPITAL N A = 0274 WITH DOT + 0323) BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL N + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ebe0	ø	O	Oslashdotbl	= U+EBE0 LATIN

			Oslash combdotbl	+ (U+EBE CAPITAL 0 = LETTER O 00D8 + WITH STROKE 0323) AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ebe1	ø	o	oslashdotbl oslash combdotbl	= U+EBE1 LATIN SMALL + (U+EBE LETTER O 1 = 00F8 WITH STROKE + 0323) AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
effc	Œ	OO	OOligdotbl OOlig combdotbl	= U+EFF LATIN + C CAPITAL (U+EFF LIGATURE OO C = WITH DOT F20A + BELOW (= 0323) LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OO + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
effd	œ	oo	ooligdotbl oolig combdotbl	= U+EFF LATIN SMALL + D LIGATURE OO (U+EFF WITH DOT D = BELOW (= F20B + LATIN SMALL 0323) LIGATURE OO + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e26d	Ɔ	P	Pdotbl combdotbl	= P + U+E26D LATIN (U+E26 CAPITAL D = LETTER P 0050 + WITH DOT 0323) BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER P + COMBINING

				DOT BELOW)
e66d	p̣	P	p̣dotbl = p + U+E66D combdotbl (U+E66D = 0070 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER P WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER P + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e288	Q̣	Q	Q̣dotbl = Q + U+E288 combdotbl (U+E288 = 0051 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Q WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Q + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e688	q̣	q	q̣dotbl = q + U+E688 combdotbl (U+E688 = 0071 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Q WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Q + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef2b	Ṛ	R	ṛscapdotbl = U+EF2B ṛscap + (U+EF2B = 0280 + 0323)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL R WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL R + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e7c1	ꝛ	r	ṛrotdotbl = U+E7C1 ṛrot + (U+E7C1 = F20E + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER ROTUNDA WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER ROTUNDA + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef2c	Ṣ	S	ṣ̣capdotbl = U+EF2C	LATIN LETTER

			sscap combdotbl	+ C (U+EF2 C EF0E + 0323)	SMALL CAPITAL S WITH DOT BELOW) LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL S + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e7c2	ƒ	s	slongdotbl slong combdotbl	= U+E7C2 + (U+E7C 2 = 017F + 0323)	LATIN LETTER LONG S WITH DOT BELOW) LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
ef2d	‡	T	tscapdotbl tscap combdotbl	= U+EF2 + D (U+EF2 D 1D1B + 0323)	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL T WITH DOT BELOW) LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL T + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e3e6	Ɔ	V	Vinsdotbl Vins combdotbl	= U+E3E6 + (U+E3E 6 = F210 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e7e6	Ʒ	v	vinsdotbl vins combdotbl	= U+E7E6 + (U+E7E 6 = F211 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL

					LETTER INSULAR V (VEND) + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e39f	þ	þ	THORNdotbl U+E39F = THORN + (U+E39 combdotbl F =	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER THORN + COMBINING DOT BELOW)	
					00DE + THORN WITH 0323) DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER THORN + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e79f	þ	þ	thorndotbl = U+E79F thorn + (U+E79 combdotbl F =	LATIN SMALL LETTER THORN WITH DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER THORN + COMBINING DOT BELOW)	
					00FE + DOT BELOW (0323) = LATIN SMALL LETTER THORN + COMBINING DOT BELOW)

7.2 Appendix T Subrange 20: Characters with diaeresis

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
effe	Ä	Ä	AA	AAliguml = AAlig combuml	U+EFFE + (U+EFFE = EF90 + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
efff	ä	ä	aa	aaliguml aalig combuml	= U+EFFF + (U+EFFF = EF91 + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AA + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
e042	Æ	Æ	AE	AEliguml = AElig combuml	U+E042 + (U+E042 = 00C6 + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
e442	æ	æ	ae	aeliguml aelig combuml	= U+E442 + (U+E442 = 00E6 + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LETTER WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
ebe2	ÿ	ÿ	J	Juml combuml	= J + U+EBE2 (U+EBE2 = 004A + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER WITH

					DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
ebe3	ÿ	j	juml = j + U+EBE3 combuml (U+EBE3 = 006A + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN SMALL LETTER J + COMBINING DIAERESIS)	
ebe4	Œ	OO	OOLiguml U+EBE4 = OOlig + (U+EBE4 combuml = F20A + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OO WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE OO + COMBINING DIAERESIS)	
ebe5	œ	oo	ooliguml = U+EBE5 oolig + (U+EBE5 combuml = F20B + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OO WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OO + COMBINING DIAERESIS)	
ebe6	Œ	PP	PPliguml = U+EBE6 PPlig + (U+EBE6 combuml = EEDD + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE PP WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE PP + COMBINING DIAERESIS)	
ebe7	œ	pp	ppliguml = U+EBE7 pplig + (U+EBE7 combuml = EED6 + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE PP WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE PP +	

e342	Ŵ	V	Vuml = V U+E342 + combuml (U+E342 = 0056 + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
e742	ŵ	v	vuml = v + U+E742 combuml (U+E742 = 0076 + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
ebe8	Ŷ	YY	YYliguml U+EBE8 = YYlig + (U+EBE8 combuml = F212 + 0308)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE YY WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE YY + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
ebe9	ŷ	yy	yyliguml = U+EBE9 yylig + (U+EBE9 combuml = F213 + 0308)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE YY WITH DIAERESIS (= LATIN SMALL LIGATURE YY + COMBINING DIAERESIS)
e8d5	ä	a	adiaguml U+E8D5	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WI TH DIAGONAL DIAERESIS
e8d7	ö	o	odiaguml U+E8D7	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WI TH DIAGONAL DIAERESIS

14.19 Appendix U Subrange 21: Characters with curl above (reversed ogonek)

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e033	Ą	Ą	A	Acurl = A + combcurl	U+E033 (U+E033 = 0041 + 1DCE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A WITH CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e433	ą	ą	a	acurl = a + combcurl	U+E433 (U+E433 = 0061 + 1DCE)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH CURL (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e0ea	Æ	Æ	AE	AEligcurl = AElig + combcurl	U+EBE (U+EBE = 00C6 + 1DCE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e0eb	æ	æ	ae	aeligcurl = aelig + combcurl	U+EBE (U+EBE = 00E6 + 1DCE)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e0e9	Ě	Ě	E	Ecurl = E + combcurl	U+E0E9 (U+E0E9 = 0045 + 1DCE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e4e9	ě	ě	e	ecurl = e + combcurl	U+E4E9 (U+E4E9 = 0045 + 1DCE)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)

				9 = 0065 WITH CURL (= + LATIN SMALL 1DCE) LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e12a	İ	I	Icurl = I + U+E12A combcurl (U+E12A	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I WITH A = 0049 CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL + 1DCE) LETTER I + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e52a	ı	i	icurl = i + U+E52A combcurl (U+E52A	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH A = 0069 CURL (= LATIN SMALL LETTER + 1DCE) I + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e163	Ĵ	J	Jcurl = J + U+E163 combcurl (U+E163	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J WITH = 0049 + CURL (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER J + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e563	ĵ	j	jcurl = j + U+E563 combcurl (U+E563	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH = 006A CURL (= LATIN SMALL LETTER + 1DCE) J + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e3d3	Ŏ	O	Ocurl = O + U+E3D3 combcurl (U+E3D3	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O 3 = 004F WITH CURL (= + LATIN CAPITAL 1DCE) LETTER O + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e7d3	ø	o	ocurl = o + U+E7D3 combcurl (U+E7D3	LATIN SMALL LETTER O 3 = 006F WITH CURL (= + LATIN SMALL 1DCE) LETTER O +

Hex	Unicode	Category	Description
e3d4	Œ	O	Oslashcurl U+E3D4 LATIN CAPITAL = Oslash + (U+E3D LETTER O combcurl 4 = WITH STROKE 00D8 + AND CURL (= 1DCE) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e7d4	œ	o	oslashcurl U+E7D4 LATIN SMALL = oslash + (U+E7D LETTER O combcurl 4 = 00F8 WITH STROKE + AND CURL (= 1DCE) LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e331	Ů	U	Ucurl = U U+E331 LATIN CAPITAL + combcurl (U+E331 LETTER U = 0055 + WITH CURL (= 1DCE) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e731	ů	u	ucurl = u + U+E731 LATIN SMALL combcurl (U+E731 LETTER U = 0075 + WITH CURL (= 1DCE) LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e385	Ÿ	Y	Ycurl = Y U+E385 LATIN CAPITAL + combcurl (U+E385 LETTER Y = 0059 + WITH CURL (= 1DCE) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE E)
e785	ÿ	y	ycurl = y + U+E785 LATIN SMALL combcurl (U+E785 LETTER Y

= 0079 + WITH CURL (=
1DCE) LATIN SMALL
LETTER Y +
COMBINING
OGONEK ABOVE
E)

14.20 Appendix V Subrange 22: Characters with ogonek

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e040	Æ		AE	AEligogon = AElig + combogon	U+E040 00C6 0328)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH OGONEK (LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING OGONEK)
e440	æ		ae	aeligogon = aelig + combogon	U+E440 00E6 0328)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH OGONEK (LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING OGONEK)
ebf0	Ȧ		AV	AVligogon = AVlig + combogon	U+EBF 0 EF96 0328)	LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV WITH OGONEK (LATIN CAPITAL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING OGONEK)
ebf1	ȷ		av	avligogon = avlig + combogon	U+EBF 1 EF97 0328)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV WITH OGONEK (LATIN SMALL LIGATURE AV + COMBINING OGONEK)
e076	Ç		C	Cogon + combogon	U+E076 (U+E076 6 = 0043 + 0328)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C WITH OGONEK (LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C + COMBINING OGONEK)
e476	ç		c	cogon = c +	U+E476	LATIN SMALL

			combogon	(U+E47 LETTER C 6 = 0063 WITH OGONEK + 0328) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER C + COMBINING OGONEK)
e255	Ø	O	Oslashogon = Oslash + combogon	U+E255 LATIN CAPITAL (U+E25 LETTER O 5 = WITH STROKE 00D8 + AND OGONEK (0328) = LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING OGONEK)
e655	ø	o	oslashogon = oslash + combogon	U+E655 LATIN SMALL (U+E65 LETTER O 5 = WITH STROKE 00F8 + AND OGONEK (0328) = LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING OGONEK)
e2ee	Ŧ	T	Togon = T+ combogon	U+E2E LATIN CAPITAL E LETTER T (U+E2E WITH OGONEK E = (= LATIN 0054 + CAPITAL 0328) LETTER T + COMBINING OGONEK)
e6ee	ț	t	togon = t + combogon	U+E6E LATIN SMALL E LETTER T (U+E6E WITH OGONEK E = (= LATIN 0074 + SMALL LETTER 0328) T + COMBINING OGONEK)

14.21 Appendix W Subrange 23: Characters with breve

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e03f	Ǽ		AE	AEligbreve = AElig + combbreve	U+E03F F 00C6 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH BREVE
e43f	ǣ		ae	aeligbreve = aelig + combbreve	U+E43F F 00E6 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH BREVE
ebee	ø		O	Oslashbreve = Oslash + combbreve	U+EBE E (U+EB EE 00D8 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND BREVE
ebef	ø		o	oslashbreve = oslash: + combbreve	U+EBE F (U+EB EF 00F8 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING BREVE)
E376	Ÿ		Y	Ybreve = Y + combbreve	U+E376 (U+E37 6 = 0054 + 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y WITH BREVE
E776	ÿ		y	ybreve = y + combbreve	U+E776 (U+E77 6 = 0079 + 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Y WITH BREVE

14.22 Appendix X Subrange 24: Characters with breve below

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e548	ı	ı	i	ibrevinvbl = i + combbrevinvbl	U+E548 (U+E548 = 0069 + 032F)	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH INVERTED BREVE BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING INVERTED BREVE BELOW)
e727	ı̣	ı̣	u	ubrevinvbl = u + combbrevinvbl	U+E727 (U+E727 = 0075 + 032F)	LATIN SMALL LETTER U WITH INVERTED BREVE BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING INVERTED BREVE BELOW)

14.23 Appendix Y Subrange 25: Characters with circumflex

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e5d7	ñ		n	ncirc = n + combcirc	U+E5D7 (U+E5D7 + 006E0302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER N WITH CIRCUMFLEX (LATIN SMALL LETTER N + COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
e33b	Ŵ		V	Vcirc = V + combcirc	U+E33B (U+E33B + 00560302)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V WITH CIRCUMFLEX (LATIN CAPITAL LETTER V + COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
e73b	ŵ		v	vcirc = v + combcirc	U+E73B (U+E73B + 00760302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH CIRCUMFLEX (LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
ebbd	ê		ea	eacombcirc = e + a + combcircdbl	U+EBB (U+EBB + 00650061+1DCD)	LATIN SMALL LETTER EA WITH CIRCUMFLEX (LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING DOUBLE CIRCUMFLEX ABOVE)
ebbe	ê		eu	eucombcirc = e + u + combcirc	U+EBB	LATIN SMALL

e + u + E LETTER EU
combcircdbl (U+EBB WITH
E = CIRCUMFLEX (
0065 + = LATIN SMALL
0075+ LETTER E +
1DCD) LATIN SMALL
LETTER U +
COMBINING
DOUBLE
CIRCUMFLEX
ABOVE)

14.24 Appendix Z Subrange 26: Characters with ring above

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e8d1	æ		ae	aeligring aelig combring	= U+E8D + 1 (U+E8D WITH 1 = ABOVE 00E6 + 030A)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH RING ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING RING ABOVE)
e4cf	ë		e	ering combring	= e + U+E4C F (U+E4C WITH F = ABOVE 0065 + 030A)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH RING ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING RING ABOVE)
e637	ö		o	oring combring	= o + U+E637 (U+E637 = WITH 006F + 030A)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH RING ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING RING ABOVE)
e743	ÿ		v	vring combring	= v + U+E743 (U+E743 = 0076 WITH + 030A)	LATIN SMALL LETTER V WITH RING ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER V + COMBINING RING ABOVE)

14.25 Appendix AA Subrange 27: Characters with ring below

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e5a4	ı	ı̇	ı	lringbl = 1 + combringbl	U+E5A4 (U+E5A4 WITH 006C + 0325)	LATIN SMALL LETTER L WITH COMBINING RING BELOW
e5c5	ṁ	ṁ	m	mringbl = m + combringbl	U+E5C5 (U+E5C5 WITH 006D + 0325)	LATIN SMALL LETTER M WITH COMBINING RING BELOW
e5ee	ṅ	ṅ	n	nringbl = n + combringbl	U+E5EE (U+E5EE WITH 006E + 0325)	LATIN SMALL LETTER N WITH COMBINING RING BELOW
e6a3	ṛ	ṛ	r	rringbl = r + combringbl	U+E6A3 (U+E6A3 WITH 0072 + 0325)	LATIN SMALL LETTER R WITH COMBINING RING BELOW

14.26 Appendix AB Subrange 28: Characters with tilde

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e68b	q̃		q	qbardestilde = qbardes + combtilde	U+E68B (U+E68B = A757+0303)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Q WITH STROKE THROUGH DESCENDER AND TILDE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Q WITH STROKE THROUGH DESCENDER+ COMBINING TILDE)

14.27 Appendix AC Subrange 29: Characters with curly bar above

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
ebbf	ũ		u	ucurlbar = i + combcurlbar	U+EBB F	LATIN SMALL LETTER U (U+EBB WITH CURLY BAR ABOVE (= U+0075 + LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING CURLY BAR ABOVE))

14.28 Appendix AD Subrange 30: Characters with vertical bar above

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e324	Ù		U	Uvertline = U + combvertline	U+E324 = 0055	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U WITH VERTICAL LINE ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING VERTICAL LINE ABOVE)
e724	ù		u	uvertline = u + combvertline	U+E724 = 0075	LATIN SMALL LETTER U WITH VERTICAL LINE ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING VERTICAL LINE ABOVE)

14.29 Appendix AE Subrange 31: Characters with superscript letters

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e02c	Å		Ae	Aesup = A + C esup	U+E02 (U+E02 C 0041 0364)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A WITH SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e42c	å		ae	aesup = a + C esup	U+E42 (U+E42 C 0061 0364)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e8e0	ä		ai	aisup = a + isup	U+E8E0 (U+E8E 0 = 0061 + 0365)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH SMALL LETTER I ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER I)
e42d	å		ao	aosup = a + D osup	U+E42 (U+E42 D 0061 0366)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH SMALL LETTER O ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)
e8e1	ä		au	ausup	U+E8E1	LATIN SMALL

				= a + (U+E8E usup 1 = 0061 + 0367) LETTER ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
e42e	ǎ	av	avsup = U+E42E a + (U+E42 vsup E = 0061 + 036E) LETTER ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)	
e0e1	Ě	Ea	Easup U+E0E1 = E + (U+E0E asup 1 = 0045 + 0363) LETTER ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER A)	
e4e1	ě	ea	easup = U+E4E1 e + (U+E4E asup 1 = 0065 + 0363) LETTER ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER A)	
e8e2	ě	ee	eesup = U+E8E2 e + (U+E8E esup 2 = 0065 + 0364) LETTER ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING LATIN SMALL	

			LETTER E)
e4e2	è	ei	<p>eisup = U+E4E2 LATIN SMALL e + isup (U+E4E LETTER E WITH 2 = 0065 LATIN SMALL + 0365) LETTER I ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER I)</p>
e8e3	ë	eo	<p>eosup U+E8E3 LATIN SMALL = e + (U+E8E LETTER E WITH osup 3 = 0065 LATIN SMALL + 0366) LETTER O ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)</p>
e4e3	ě	ev	<p>evsup = U+E4E3 LATIN SMALL e + (U+E4E LETTER E WITH vsup 3 = 0065 LATIN SMALL + 036E) LETTER V ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)</p>
e8e4	ì	ia	<p>iasup = U+E8E4 LATIN SMALL i + asup (U+E8E LETTER I WITH 4 = 0069 LATIN SMALL + 0363) LETTER A ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER A)</p>
e54a	ï	ie	<p>iesup = U+E54A LATIN SMALL i + esup (U+E54 LETTER I WITH A = LATIN SMALL 0069 + LETTER E 0364) ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I +</p>

				COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e8e5	ï	io	iosup = U+E8E5 i + osup (U+E8E5 5 = 0069 + 0366)	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER O ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)
e8e6	ï̇	iu	iusup = U+E8E6 i + usup (U+E8E6 6 = 0069 + 0367)	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER U ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
e54b	ï̈	iv	ivsup = U+E54B i + vsup (U+E54 B = 0069 + 036E)	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER V ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)
e8e7	ĵ	je	jesup = U+E8E7 j + esup (U+E8E7 7 = 006A + 0364)	LATIN SMALL LETTER J WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER J + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e8e8	ĩ	me	mesup = U+E8E8 = m + (U+E8E8 esup 8 = 006D + 0364)	LATIN SMALL LETTER M WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (=

					LATIN SMALL LETTER M + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e643	ö	oa	oasup = o + (U+E643)	U+E643	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER A ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER A)
e244	Ö	Oe	Oesup = O + (U+E244)	U+E244	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e644	ö	oe	oesup = o + (U+E644)	U+E644	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e645	ï	oi	oisup = o + isup (U+E645)	U+E645	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER I ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER I)
e8e9	ö	oo	oosup = o + (U+E8E9)	U+E8E9	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER O ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)

				+ 0366)	SMALL LETTER O ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)
e246	Ö		Ou	Ousup = O + (U+E246)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER U ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
				usup 6 = 004F	WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER U ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
e646	ö	ü	ou	ousup = o + (U+E646)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER U ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
				usup 6 = 006F	WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER U ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
e647	ö	ü	ov	ovsup = o + (U+E647)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER V ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)
				vsup 7 = 006F	WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER V ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)
e8ea	ř	ř	re	resup = U+E8E	LATIN SMALL LETTER R WITH LATIN SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER R + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
				r + esup A	0072 + ABOVE (= 036E)

e8eb	ú	á	ua	uasup = u + asup	U+E8E LATIN SMALL LETTER U (U+E8E WITH B = 0075 SMALL LETTER A ABOVE (+ 0363) = LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER A)
e32b	Ū		Ue	Uesup = U + esup	U+E32B LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U (U+E32B WITH B = 0055 SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (+ 0364) = LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e72b	ü		ue	uesup = u + esup	U+E72B LATIN SMALL LETTER U (U+E72B WITH B = 0075 SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (+ 0364) = LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)
e72c	ÿ		ui	uisup = u + isup	U+E72C LATIN SMALL LETTER U (U+E72C WITH C = 0075 + I ABOVE (+ 0365) = LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER I)
e32d	Ŭ		Uo	Uosup = U + osup	U+E32D LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U (U+E32D WITH D = 0055 + O ABOVE (+ 0366) = LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING

						LATIN SMALL LETTER O)
e72d	ũ	uo	uosup = u + D	U+E72	LATIN LETTER U	
			osup	(U+E72 WITH D	LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)	
				0075 + O ABOVE (= 0366)		
e8ec	ŭ	uv	uvsup = u + C	U+E8E	LATIN LETTER U	
			vsup	(U+E8E WITH C	LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)	
				0075 + V ABOVE (= 036E)		
e8ed	ŵ	uw	uwsup = u + D	U+E8E	LATIN LETTER U	
			wsup	(U+E8E WITH D	LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER W)	
				0075 + W ABOVE (= F03C)		
e781	ÿ	ye	yesup = U+E781 + (U+E781 = 0079 + 0364)	U+E781	LATIN LETTER Y WITH ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Y + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)	
e8f0	Ẃ	wa	wasup = w + (U+E8F0 = 0077 + 0363)	U+E8F0	LATIN LETTER W WITH ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL	

				LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER A)
e353	Ŵ	We	Wesup U+E353 LATIN CAPITAL = W + (U+E35 LETTER W esup 3 = 0057 WITH LATIN + 0364) SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)	
e753	ŵ	we	wesup U+E753 LATIN SMALL = w + (U+E75 LETTER W esup 3 = 0077 WITH LATIN + 0364) SMALL LETTER E ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER E)	
e8f1	ŵ	wi	wisup U+E8F1 LATIN SMALL = w + (U+E8F LETTER W isup 1 = 0077 WITH LATIN + 0365) SMALL LETTER I ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER I)	
e754	ŵ	wo	wosup U+E754 LATIN SMALL = w + (U+E75 LETTER W osup 4 = 0077 WITH LATIN + 0366) SMALL LETTER O ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER O)	
e8f2	ŵ	wu	wusup U+E8F2 LATIN SMALL = w + (U+E8F LETTER W usup 2 = 0077 WITH LATIN + 0367) SMALL LETTER	

					U ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER U)
e8f3	ŵ	wv	wvsup	U+E8F3	LATIN SMALL = w + (U+E8F3 LETTER W vsup 3 = 0077 WITH LATIN + 036E) SMALL LETTER V ABOVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER W + COMBINING LATIN SMALL LETTER V)

14.30 Appendix AF Subrange 32: Characters with acute accent and dot above

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Standardized Character	Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
ebf4	Ǻ		A	Adotacute + combdot combacute	A U+EBF 4 = 0041 + 0307+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A WITH DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE ACCENT)
ebf5	ǻ		a	adotacute + combdot combacute	a U+EBF 5 = 0061 + 0307+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE ACCENT)
e0c8	Ě		E	Edotacute + combdot combacute	E U+E0C 8 = 0045 + 0307+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE ACCENT)
e4c8	ě		e	edotacute	e U+E4C	LATIN SMALL

			+ combdot + 8	LETTER E
			combacute (U+E4C WITH DOT	
			8 = 0065 ABOVE AND	
			+ 0307+ ACUTE (=	
			0301) LATIN SMALL	
			LETTER E +	
			COMBINING	
			DOT ABOVE+	
			COMBINING	
			ACUTE	
			ACCENT)	
ebf6	Ī	I	Idotacute = I + U+EBF	LATIN
			combdot + 6	CAPITAL
			combacute (U+EBF LETTER I	
			6 = 0049 WITH DOT	
			+ 0307+ ABOVE AND	
			0301) ACUTE (=	
			LATIN	
			CAPITAL	
			LETTER I +	
			COMBINING	
			DOT ABOVE+	
			COMBINING	
			ACUTE	
			ACCENT)	
ebf7	ĩ	i	idotacute = i + U+EBF	LATIN SMALL
			combdot + 7	LETTER I
			combacute (U+EBF WITH DOT	
			7 = 0069 ABOVE AND	
			+ 0307+ ACUTE (=	
			0301) LATIN SMALL	
			LETTER I +	
			COMBINING	
			DOT ABOVE+	
			COMBINING	
			ACUTE	
			ACCENT)	
ebf8	Ŏ	O	Odotacute = O U+EBF	LATIN
			+ combdot + 8	CAPITAL
			combacute (U+EBF LETTER O	
			8 = WITH DOT	
			004F + ABOVE AND	
			0307+ ACUTE (=	
			0301) LATIN	
			CAPITAL	
			LETTER O +	
			COMBINING	
			DOT ABOVE+	

				COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
ebf9	ö	o	odotacute = o + combdot + 9 combacute (U+EBF 9 = 006F + 0307+ 0301)	U+EBF LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE (=
ebfc	ø	O	Oslashdotacute = O + combdot + 00D8 combacute C = 0307+ 0301)	U+EBF LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE (=
ebfd	ø	o	oslashdotacute = o + combdot + 00F8 combacute D = 0307+ 0301)	U+EBF LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE (=
ebfe	Ů	U	Udotacute = U + combdot + E combacute (U+EBF E = 0055 +	U+EBF LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U WITH DOT ABOVE AND

				0307+ ACUTE (= 0301) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING DOT ABOVE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e384	ÿ	Y	Ydotacute = Y U+EBF LATIN SMALL + combdot + F LETTER U combacute (U+EBF WITH DOT F = ABOVE AND 0075 + ACUTE (= 0307+ LATIN SMALL 0301) LETTER U + COMBINING DOT ABOVE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	
e384	Ÿ	Y	Ydotacute = Y U+E384 LATIN + combdot + (U+E38 CAPITAL combacute 4 = 0059 LETTER Y + 0307+ WITH DOT 0301) ABOVE AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y + COMBINING DOT ABOVE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	
e784	ÿ	y	ydotacute = y U+E784 LATIN SMALL + combdot + (U+E78 LETTER Y combacute 4 = 0079 WITH DOT + 0307+ ABOVE AND 0301) ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Y + COMBINING DOT ABOVE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)	

14.31 Appendix AG Subrange 33: Characters with acute accent and dot below

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e498	é		e	edotblacut = E + combdotbl + 8 = combacute + 0323+	U+E498 (U+E49 0065 + 0323+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH DOT BELOW AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING DOT BELOW+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)

14.32 Appendix AH Subrange 34: Characters with acute accent and diaeresis

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e62c	ó		o	oumlacute = o + combuml + combacute	= U+E62 C (U+E62 C = 006F + 0308+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH DIAERESIS AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING DIAERESIS+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)

14.33 Appendix A1 Subrange 35: Characters with acute accent and curl above (reversed ogonek)

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
ebb7	Ŏ		Ŏ	Ocurlacute = Ŏ combcurl + = combacute	U+EBB7 + (U+EBB7 + 004F + 1DCE+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH CURL AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Ŏ + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
ebb8	ö		ö	ocurlacute = ö combcurl + = combacute	U+EBB8 + (U+EBB8 + 006F + 1DCE+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH CURL AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Ŏ + COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE+ COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)

14.34 Appendix AJ Subrange 36: Characters with acute accent and ogonek

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e004	Ą		A	Aogonacute + combogon combacute	A U+E004 + (U+E004 = 0041) + 0328+0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER WITH OGONEK AND ACUTE ACCENT) (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e404	ą		a	aogonacute + combogon combacute	a U+E404 + (U+E404 = 0061) + 0328+0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER WITH OGONEK AND ACUTE ACCENT) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e8d3	ą̇		ae	aeligogonacute aelig combogon combacute	= U+E8D3 + 3 + (U+E8D3 = 00E6) + 0328+0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH OGONEK AND ACUTE ACCENT) (= LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e099	Ę		E	Eogonacute + combogon combacute	E U+E099 + (U+E099 = 0045)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER

				+ 0328+ WITH 0301) OGONEK AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e499	é	e	eogonacut + combogon combacut	= e U+E499 LATIN SMALL + (U+E49 LETTER E 9 = 0065 WITH + 0328+ OGONEK AND 0301) ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e20c	Ŏ	O	Oogonacut + combogon combacut	= O U+E20 LATIN + C CAPITAL (U+E20 LETTER O C = WITH 004F + OGONEK AND 0328 + ACUTE (= 0301) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e60c	ó	o	oogonacut + combogon combacut	= o U+E60 LATIN SMALL + C LETTER O (U+E60 WITH C = OGONEK AND 006F + ACUTE (= 0328 + LATIN SMALL 0301) LETTER O + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING ACUTE

					ACCENT)
e257	Ø	○	Oslashogonacut	U+E257	LATIN
			= Oslash	+ (U+E25	CAPITAL
			combogon	+ 7	= LETTER ○
			combacut	00D8 +	WITH STROKE
				0328+	AND OGONEK
				0301)	AND ACUTE (
				=	LATIN
					CAPITAL
					LETTER ○
					WITH STROKE
					+ COMBINING
					OGONEK +
					COMBINING
					ACUTE
					ACCENT)
e657	ø	○	oslashogonacut	U+E657	LATIN SMALL
			= oslash	+ (U+E65	LETTER ○
			combogon	+ 7	= WITH STROKE
			combacut	00F8 +	AND OGONEK
				0328+	AND ACUTE (
				0301)	= LATIN
					SMALL
					LETTER ○
					WITH STROKE
					+ COMBINING
					OGONEK +
					COMBINING
					ACUTE
					ACCENT)

14.35 Appendix AK Subrange 37: Characters with double acute accent and ogonek

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e0ea	Ĕ	Ĕ	E	Eogondblac E + combogon comdblac	= U+E0E A + (U+E0E A = 0045 + 0328+ 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
e4ea	ĕ	ĕ	e	eogondblac e + combogon + comdblac	= U+E4E A (U+E4E A = 0065 + 0328+ 030B)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc4	Œ	Œ	O	Oogondblac = Œ combogon comdblac	U+EBC + 4 + (U+EBC 4 = 004F + 0328+ 030B)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH OGONEK AND DOUBLE ACUTE ACCENT)

					ACUTE ACCENT)
ebc5	õ	o	oogondblac	= U+EBC	LATIN SMALL
			o	+ 5	LETTER O
			combogon	+ (U+EBC	WITH OGONEK
			comdblac	5 = 006F	AND DOUBLE
				+ 328+	ACUTE (=
				030B)	LATIN SMALL
					LETTER O +
					COMBINING
					OGONEK+
					COMBINING
					DOUBLE
					ACUTE
					ACCENT)

14.36 Appendix AL Subrange 38: Characters with dot above and ogonek

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e0eb	Ę		E	Eogondot E combogon combdot	= U+E0E + B (U+E0E B = AND 0045 + ABOVE 0328+ 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOT ABOVE) (=
e4eb	ę		e	eogondot e combogon combdot	= U+E4E + B (U+E4E B = AND 0065 + ABOVE 0328 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOT ABOVE) (=
ebde	Ń		Ń	Oogondot O combogon combdot	= U+EBD + E (U+EB DE = AND 004F + ABOVE 0328 0307)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Ń WITH OGONEK AND DOT ABOVE) (=
ebdf	ń		ń	oogondot o combogon combdot	= U+EBD + F (U+EB DF = AND 006F + ABOVE 0328 0307)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Ń WITH OGONEK AND DOT ABOVE) (=

OGONEK +
COMBINING
DOT ABOVE)

14.37 Appendix AM Subrange 39: Characters with dot below and ogonek

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e0e8	Ę	Ę	E	Eogondotbl = E combogon + 8 = 0045	U+E0E8 + (U+E0E + 0328 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e4e8	ę	ę	e	eogondotbl = e combogon + 8 = 0065	U+E4E8 + (U+E4E + 0328 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK + COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e208	Ų	Ų	Ų	Oogondotbl = Ų combogon + 8 = 004F	U+E208 + (U+E20 + 0328 + 0323)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Ų WITH OGONEK AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Ų + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING DOT BELOW)
e608	ų	ų	o	oogondotbl = o combogon + 8 = 006F	U+E608 + (U+E60 + 0328 + 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Ų WITH OGONEK AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER Ų + COMBINING

OGONEK +
COMBINING
DOT BELOW)

14.38 Appendix AN Subrange 40: Characters with diaeresis and macron

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e4cd	ē		e	eumlmacr e combuml combmacr	= U+E4C + D + (U+E4C D 0065 0308+ 0304)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH DIAERESIS AND MACRON (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING DIAERESIS+ COMBINING MACRON)

14.39 Appendix AO Subrange 41: Characters with diaeresis and circumflex

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e41a	â		a	aumlcirc a combuml combcirc	= U+E41 + A + (U+E41 A 0061 0308+ 0302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DIAERESIS AND CIRCUMFLEX (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING DIAERESIS+ COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
e22d	Ô		O	Oumlcirc O combuml combcirc	= U+E22 + D + (U+E22 D 004F 0308+ 0302)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH DIAERESIS AND CIRCUMFLEX (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING DIAERESIS+ COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
e62d	ô		o	oumlcirc o combuml combcirc	= U+E62 + D + (U+E62 D 006F 0308+ 0302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH DIAERESIS AND CIRCUMFLEX (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING DIAERESIS+ COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
e317	Û		U	Uumlcirc U combuml combcirc	= U+E317 + (U+E31 + 7 = 0055 + 0308+)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U WITH DIAERESIS AND

			0302)	CIRCUMFLEX (
			=	LATIN
				CAPITAL
				LETTER U +
				COMBINING
				DIAERESIS+
				COMBINING
				CIRCUMFLEX
				ACCENT)
e717	û	u	uumlcirc	= U+E717 LATIN SMALL
			u	+ (U+E71 LETTER U
			combuml	+ 7 = 0075 WITH
			combcirc	+ 0308+ DIAERESIS AND
			0302)	CIRCUMFLEX (
			=	LATIN SMALL
				LETTER U +
				COMBINING
				DIAERESIS+
				COMBINING
				CIRCUMFLEX
				ACCENT)

14.40 Appendix AP Subrange 42: Characters with diaeresis and dot below

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e41d	ä		a	adotbluml a + combuml + combdotbl	= U+E41 D (U+E41 D 0061 0308+ 0323)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH DIAERESIS AND DOT BELOW (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING DIAERESIS+ COMBINING DOT BELOW)

14.41 Appendix AQ Subrange 43: Characters with ogonek and curl above (reversed ogonek)

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
ebf2	Ě		E	Eogoncurl E combogon combcurl	= U+EBF + 2 + (U+EBF WITH OGONEK AND CURL (= 0045 + 0328+ 1DCE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND CURL (= 0328+ LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
ebf3	ě		e	eogoncurl e combogon combcurl	= U+EBF + 3 + (U+EBF WITH OGONEK AND CURL (= 0065 + 0328+ 1DCE)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND CURL (= 0328+ LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e24f	Ŏ		O	Oogoncurl = O combogon combcurl	U+E24F + (U+E24F + 004F + 0328+ 1DCE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH OGONEK AND CURL (= 0328+ LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING OGONEK ABOVE)
e64f	ȯ		o	oogoncurl o combogon combcurl	= U+E64F + (U+E64F + 006F + 0328+ 1DCE)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH OGONEK AND CURL (= 0328+ LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING

OGONEK+
COMBINING
OGONEK ABOVE
E)

7.3 Appendix AR Subrange 44: Characters with ogonek and circumflex

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e49f	ê		e	eogoncirc e combogon combcirc	= U+E49F + (U+E49 + F 0065 0328+ 0302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND CIRCUMFLEX (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)
e60e	ô		o	oogoncirc o combogon combcirc	= U+E60E + (U+E60 + E 006F 0328+ 0302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH OGONEK AND CIRCUMFLEX (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)

14.42 Appendix AS Subrange 45: Characters with ring above and circumflex

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e41f	â		a	aringcirc a combring combcirc	= U+E41F + (U+E41 + F = 0061 + 030A+ 0302)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH RING ABOVE AND CIRCUMFLEX (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING RING ABOVE+ COMBINING CIRCUMFLEX ACCENT)

7.4 Appendix AT Subrange 46: Characters with macron and breve

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e010	Ă		A	Amacrbreve + combmacr combbreve	= A U+E010 + (U+E01 0 = 0041 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e4410	ă		a	amacrbreve + combmacr combbreve	= a U+E410 + (U+E41 0 = 0061 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING

e03d	Ä	AE	AEligmacrbreve = AElig combmacr combbreve	U+E03 + D (U+E03 D 00C6 0304+ 0306)	BREVE) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE = WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e43d	ä	ae	aeligmacrbreve aelig combmacr combbreve	= U+E43 + D (U+E43 D 00E6 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER AE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e0b7	Ë	E	Emacrbreve + combmacr combbreve	= E U+E0B + 7 (U+E0B 7 = 0045 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e4b7	ë	e	emacrbreve + combmacr combbreve	= e U+E4B + 7 (U+E4B 7 = 0065 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e137	Ï	I	Imacrbreve combmacr	= I + U+E137 + (U+E13	LATIN CAPITAL

			combbreve	7 = 0049 LETTER I + 0304+ WITH 0306) MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e537	ĩ	I	imacrbreve = i + U+E537 combmacr + (U+E53 combbreve 7 = 0069 + 0304+ MACRON AND 0306) BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)	
e21b	Ŏ	O	Omacrbreve = O U+E21 + combmacr + B combbreve (U+E21 LETTER O B = WITH 004F + MACRON AND 0304+ BREVE (= 0306) LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)	
e61b	õ	o	omacrbreve = o U+E61 + combmacr + B combbreve (U+E61 WITH B = MACRON AND 006F + BREVE (= 0304+ LATIN SMALL 0306) LETTER O + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)	
e260	Œ	OE	OEligmacrbreve U+E260 = OElig + (U+E26 CAPITAL combmacr + 0 = 0152 LIGATURE OE combbreve + 0304+ WITH 0306) MACRON AND BREVE (=	

					LATIN CAPITAL LETTER OE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e660	œ	oe	oeligmacrbreve = oelig combmacr combbreve	U+E660 + (U+E66 + 0 = 0153 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LIGATURE OE WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER OE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e253	Œ	O	Oslashmacrbreve = Oslash combmacr combbreve	U+E253 + (U+E25 + 3 = 00D8 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e653	ø	o	oslashmacrbreve = oslash combmacr combbreve	U+E653 + (U+E65 + 3 = 00F8 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e30b	Ů	U	Umacrbreve + combmacr combbreve	= U U+E30 + B (U+E30 B = 0055 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U WITH MACRON AND BREVE (= LATIN CAPITAL

					LETTER U + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)
e70b	ũ	u	umacrbreve = u + combmacr + B combbreve	U+E70 (U+E70 B = 0075 + 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER U WITH MACRON AND BREVE (=
e375	Ÿ	Y	Ymacrbreve = Y + combmacr + combbreve	U+E375 (U+E37 5 = 0304+ 0306)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y WITH MACRON AND BREVE (=
e775	ÿ	y	ymacrbreve = y + combmacr + combbreve	U+E775 (U+E77 5 = 0304+ 0306)	LATIN SMALL LETTER Y WITH MACRON AND BREVE (=
					LATIN SMALL LETTER Y + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING BREVE)

14.43 Appendix AU Subrange 47: Characters with macron and acute accent

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e00a	À		A	Amacracute + combmacr combacute	A U+E00 + A (U+E00 A 0041 + 0304+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A WITH MACRON AND ACUTE (= CAPITAL LETTER A + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
e40a	á		a	amacracute + combmacr combacute	a U+E40 + A (U+E40 A 0061 + 0304+ 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER A WITH MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER A + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
e03a	Æ		AE	AEligmacracute = AElig combmacr combacute	U+E03 + A (U+E03 A 00C6 + 0304+ 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER AE WITH MACRON AND ACUTE (= CAPITAL LETTER AE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
e43a	æ		ae	aeligmacracute = aelig combmacr combacute	U+E43 + A (U+E43 A	LATIN SMALL LETTER AE WITH MACRON AND

				00E6 + ACUTE (= 0304+ LATIN SMALL 0301) LETTER AE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
e135	Ī	I	Imacracute = I + U+E135 combmacr + (U+E13 combacute 5 = 0049	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I WITH MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER I + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
e535	í	i	imacracute = i + U+E535 combmacr + (U+E53 combacute 5 = 0069	LATIN SMALL LETTER I WITH MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER I + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
ebec	Œ	O	Oslashmacracute U+EBE = Oslash + C combmacr + (U+EB combacute EC =	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE AND MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
ebed	ø	o	oslashmacracute U+EBE = oslash + D combmacr + (U+EB	LATIN SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE

				combacute	ED = AND MACRON 00F8 + AND ACUTE (0304+ = LATIN 0301) SMALL LETTER O WITH STROKE + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)
e309	Ū	U	U	Umacracute = U U+E309 + combmacr + (U+E30 combacute 9 = 0055 + 0304+ WITH 0301) MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER U WITH STROKE AND COMBINING ACUTE)
e709	ū	u	u	umacracute = u U+E709 + combmacr + (U+E70 combacute 9 = 0075 + 0304+ WITH 0301) MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER U + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)	LATIN SMALL LETTER U WITH STROKE AND COMBINING ACUTE)
e373	Ÿ	Y	Y	Ymacracute = Y U+E373 + combmacr + (U+E37 combacute 3 = 0059 + 0304+ WITH 0301) MACRON AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y + COMBINING MACRON + COMBINING ACUTE)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Y WITH STROKE AND COMBINING ACUTE)
e773	ÿ	y	y	ymacracute = y U+E773	LATIN SMALL

+ combmacr + (U+E77 LETTER Y
 combacute 3 = 0079 WITH
 + 0304+ MACRON AND
 0301) ACUTE (=
 LATIN SMALL
 LETTER Y +
 COMBINING
 MACRON +
 COMBINING
 ACUTE)

7.5 Appendix AV Subrange 48: Characters with ogonek, dot above and acute accent

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image of Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
e0ec	Ě		E	Eogondotacute = E combogon combdot combacute	U+E0E + C + (U+E0E + C 0045 0328+ 0307 0301)	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE (= LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING DOT ABOVE + COMBINING ACUTE ACCENT)
e4ec	ě		e	eogondotacute = e combogon combdot combacute	U+E4E + C + (U+E4E + C 0065 0328+ 0307 0301)	LATIN SMALL LETTER E WITH OGONEK AND DOT ABOVE AND ACUTE (= LATIN SMALL LETTER E + COMBINING OGONEK+ COMBINING DOT ABOVE + COMBINING ACUTE

					ACCENT)
ebfa	Ö	O	Oogondotacute	U+EBF	LATIN
			= O	+ A	CAPITAL
			combogon	+ (U+EBF	LETTER O
			combdot	+ A	= WITH OGONEK
			combacute	004F	+ AND DOT
				0328+	ABOVE AND
				0307	+ ACUTE (=
				0301)	LATIN
					CAPITAL
					LETTER O +
					COMBINING
					OGONEK+
					COMBINING
					DOT ABOVE +
					COMBINING
					ACUTE
					ACCENT)
ebfb	ö	o	oogondotacute	U+EBF	LATIN SMALL
			= o	+ B	LETTER O
			combogon	+ (U+EBF	WITH OGONEK
			combdot	+ B	= AND DOT
			combacute	006F	+ ABOVE AND
				0328+	ACUTE (=
				0307	+ LATIN SMALL
				0301)	LETTER O +
					COMBINING
					OGONEK+
					COMBINING
					DOT ABOVE +
					COMBINING
					ACUTE
					ACCENT)

14.44 Appendix AW Subrange 51: Alphabetical list of variant letter forms

Character ID	Unicode Character	Image Character	of Standardized Replacement	MUFI Entity	Unicode PUA Code Point	Description
f13a	Ā		A	Asqu	U+F13A	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A SQUARE FORM
f214	ɑ		a	aunc	U+F214	LATIN SMALL LETTER A UNCIAL FORM
f201	Δ		A	Ains	U+F201	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER A INSULAR FORM
f200	α		a	ains	U+F200	LATIN SMALL LETTER A INSULAR FORM
f202	ɑ		a	aopen	U+F202	LATIN SMALL LETTER OPEN A CAROLINGIAN FORM
f215	ɑ		a	aneckless	U+F215	LATIN SMALL LETTER NECKLESS A
f203	ɑ		a	aclose	U+F203	LATIN SMALL LETTER CLOSED A GOTHIC FORM
f106	Ĉ		C	Csqu	U+F106	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER C SQUARE FORM
f198	ç		c	ccurl	U+F198	LATIN SMALL LETTER C WITH CURL
f193	ċ		d	dcurl	U+F193	LATIN SMALL LETTER D WITH CURL
f10a	Ē		E	Eunc	U+F10A	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER E UNCIAL FORM
f217	Ē		E	Euncclose	U+F217	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER CLOSED E UNCIAL FORM

f218	€	€	e	eunc	U+F218	LATIN SMALL LETTER E UNCIAL FORM
f219	e	e	e	eext	U+F219	LATIN SMALL LETTER E EXTENDED BAR FORM
f21a	e	e	e	etall	U+F21A	LATIN SMALL LETTER E TALL FORM
f21b	ƒ	ƒ	f	finssemiclose	U+F21B	LATIN SMALL LETTER SEMI-CLOSED INSULAR F
f21c	ƒ	ƒ	f	finsdothook	U+F21C	LATIN SMALL LETTER INSULAR F WITH DOTTED HOOKS
f207	ƒ	ƒ	f	finsclose	U+F207	LATIN SMALL LETTER CLOSED INSULAR F
f194	ƒ	ƒ	f	fcurl	U+F194	LATIN SMALL LETTER F WITH CURL
f10e	Ɔ	Ɔ	G	Gsqu	U+F10E	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER G SQUARE FORM
f196	g	g	g	gcurl	U+F196	LATIN SMALL LETTER G WITH CURL
f21d	g	g	g	gdivloop	U+F21D	LATIN SMALL LETTER G WITH SEPARATE LOOPS
f21e	g		g	gglowloop	U+F21E	LATIN SMALL LETTER CLOSED G WITH LARGE LOWER LOOP
f21f	g		g	gsmllowloop	U+F21F	LATIN SMALL LETTER CLOSED G WITH SMALL LOWER LOOP

f110	Ĥ	H	Hunc	U+F110	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER H UNCIAL FORM
f23a	ĥ	h	hrdes	U+F23A	LATIN SMALL LETTER H WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f220	ı	i	ilong	U+F220	LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG I
f208	ķ	k	kunc	U+F208	LATIN SMALL LETTER K UNCIAL FORM
f221	ķ	k	ksemiclose	U+F221	LATIN SMALL LETTER K SEMI-CLOSED FORM
f209	ķ̄	k	kclose	U+F209	LATIN SMALL LETTER K CLOSED FORM
f195	ķ̅	k	kcurl	U+F195	LATIN SMALL LETTER K WITH CURL
f222	ł	l	ldes	U+F222	LATIN SMALL LETTER L DESCENDING
f11a	Œ	M	Munc	U+F11A	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER M UNCIAL FORM
f224	Œ̄	M	Muncdes	U+F224	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER M UNCIAL FORM WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f225	œ	m	munc	U+F225	LATIN SMALL LETTER M UNCIAL FORM
f226	œ̄	m	muncdes	U+F226	LATIN SMALL LETTER M UNCIAL FORM WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f223	ơ	m	mrdes	U+F223	LATIN SMALL LETTER M WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f229	Ŋ	N	Nrdes	U+F229	LATIN CAPITAL

						LETTER N WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f228	ŋ		n	nrdes	U+F228	LATIN SMALL LETTER N WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f22a	Ŋ		N	nscaprdes	U+F22A	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL N WITH RIGHT DESCENDER
f22b	Ŋ		N	nscapldes	U+F22B	LATIN LETTER SMALL CAPITAL N WITH LEFT DESCENDER
f19a	ñ	ñ	n	nflour	U+F19A	LATIN SMALL LETTER N WITH FLOURISH
f22c	Ŧ	Ŧ	Q	Qstem	U+F22C	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER Q WITH STEM
f19b	ŕ	ŕ	r	rflour	U+F19B	LATIN SMALL LETTER R WITH FLOURISH
f126	Ŧ	Ŧ	S	Sclose	U+F126	LATIN CAPITAL LETTER S CLOSED FORM
f128	ŧ	ŧ	s	sclose	U+F128	LATIN SMALL LETTER S CLOSED FORM
f127	Ŧ	Ŧ	s	slongdes	U+F127	LATIN SMALL LETTER LONG S DESCENDING
f199	ŧ	ŧ	t	tcurl	U+F199	LATIN SMALL LETTER T WITH CURL
f232	ŧ	ŧ	x	xldes	U+F232	LATIN SMALL LETTER X WITH LEFT DESCENDER
f233	ŧ	ŧ	y	yrgmainstrok	U+F233	LATIN SMALL LETTER Y WITH RIGHT

MAIN STROKE